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Investigation into oxide-phosphates of selected lanthanoids and transition metals

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Bonn, den 31.08.2022

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1 Introduction

1.1 Lanthanoid phosphates

In the ternary system $Ln/P/O$ many phosphates $Ln_xP_yO_z$ are already known. ICSD [1] reports results of crystal structure analyses for eight of these phases with more than 40 members. However, literature references for more phases exist. Phosphates with divalent, trivalent and mixed-valent europium $Eu^{II}_3(PO_4)_2$ [2, 3], $Eu^{III}_3O_3(PO_4)$ [3, 4], $Eu^{III}(PO_4)$ [5], $Eu^{III}(PO_3)_3$ [3, 6], $Eu^{III}_2P_4O_{13}$ [3], $Eu^{III}P_5O_{14}$ [7] and $Eu^{II}_3Eu^{III}(PO_4)_3$ [3, 8] are named. Most of the other lanthanoids form exclusively phosphates with the trivalent cations Ln^{3+} similar to those mentioned for europium. Furthermore, the phosphates $Ce^{IV}P_2O_7$ [9], $Ce^{IV}(PO_3)_4$ [10] and $Ce^{IV}O(PO_4)_2$ [11] with cerium in the oxidation state +IV are known. This brief review shows the variety of lanthanoid phosphates. However, there are lanthanoid oxide-phosphates reported by Serra *et al.* [4] several decades ago where no crystal structure data is available. In the last years, lanthanoid phosphates have gained importance in technical applications which triggered our interest in this field. The repository of nuclear waste is an important potential use. By immobilisation of radionuclides with the help of solid matrices formed by lanthanoid containing phosphates (like $M^{II}_3Ln^{III}(PO_4)_3$, with $M = Sr$ or Ba) the nuclear waste can be safely contained [12]. The class of the lanthanoid oxide-phosphates discussed in this work are promising candidates for those solid matrices. They tend to be of high inertness combined with high thermal stability. Another application is found in the field of luminescent materials in which the lanthanoid containing compounds act as dopant [13].

On the basis of Serra's work a diagram for the system $Ln_2O_3-LnPO_4$ is constructed [4]. Figure 1 illustrates the ratio between Ln_2O_3 and $LnPO_4$ with a value x . The composition can be calculated with $(Ln_2O_3)_{1-x}(LnPO_4)_x$.

Serra *et al.* studied compounds including most of the rare-earth elements except scandium, cerium and promethium [4, 14]. For europium they obtained three different oxide-phosphates to which they ascribed the compositions $Eu^{III}_3O_3(PO_4)$, $Eu^{III}_7O_6(PO_4)_3$ and $Eu^{III}_8O_9(PO_4)_2$ [4]. Despite the technical interest and the rather large number of compounds there is no information supplied on crystal structures except for the isostructural $Nd^{III}_3O_3(PO_4)$ and $Eu^{III}_3O_3(PO_4)$.

Figure 1: Compositional diagram of the Ln_2O_3 - $LnPO_4$ system with the lanthanoid oxide-phosphates identified by Serra *et al.* [4]. $Ln_{12}O_{15}(PO_4)_2$ with Ln : Tb-Lu, $Ln_8O_9(PO_4)_2$ with Ln : Sm-Lu, $Ln_3O_3(PO_4)$ with Ln : La-Tm and $Ln_7O_6(PO_4)_3$ with Ln : La-Tb.

There are several procedures to obtain lanthanoid oxide-phosphates, for example by thermal degradation or via solid state reactions. Thermal degradation of the orthophosphate ($LnPO_4$) at temperatures around 1700 °C leads to the formation of the corresponding lanthanoid oxide-phosphate after elimination of gaseous P_4O_{10} . Thermal degradation of $LnPO_4$ at temperatures above 2000 °C results in the corresponding oxide Ln_2O_3 . Besides the thermal degradation reaction, the solid state reactions between lanthanoid sesquioxides and ammoniumdihydrogenphosphate ($NH_4H_2PO_4$) or between the oxides and corresponding orthophosphates ($LnPO_4$) are common pathways to synthesize lanthanoid oxide-phosphates [4].

1.2 Anion centered coordination polyhedra

Paul Pfeiffer has adapted the 'Wernersche Koordinationslehre' to crystal chemistry by introducing a depiction of crystal structures by condensed coordination polyhedra [15, 16]. These coordination polyhedra and their linkage allow a clear and comprehensive picture of most crystal structures. They can be formed with cations or anions as central atoms. The so-called anti-type, in which the polyhedra have anions as their central atoms help to explain complex structures [15, 17].

The most common anions forming $[XM_4]$ tetrahedra are O^{2-} and N^{3-} whereas halogens are rarely the central ions [17]. The conventional Pauling radius for the O^{2-} ion is 1,38 Å [18] with an average distance between the oxide anion and metal cation $d(M-O)$ of 2,4 Å [19] which can be found in lanthanoid oxide-phosphates.

In the structures of rare-earth oxo-salts and of the oxides themselves $[\text{OM}_4]$ tetrahedra are a common structure motif. The connection of these tetrahedra with each other is mostly created via edges, resulting in polycationic layers. Hereby, the number of shared edges may vary from compound to compound [19]. Comparison of the structure motifs of MOCl and A-type M_2O_3 with $\text{M} = \text{Eu}$ is shown in figure 3. Both structure motifs are visualized with emphasis to the layered structure in (a) and (c). In the case of EuOCl (SG: $P4/nmm$ (no. 129), $Z = 2$) the layers are separated by Cl^- ions. A connectivity via four edges of each tetrahedron $[\text{OEu}_4]$ is present. The connectivity of the tetrahedra $[\text{OEu}_4]$ in Eu_2O_3 (A-type, SG: $P\bar{3}m1$ (no. 164), $Z = 2$) is established via three edges each. The peculiarity of A-type Eu_2O_3 is the formation of the tetrahedral units, which are separated by oxide ions. These oxide ions between the layers are further apart, leading to a coordination number of six resulting in octahedra visualized in (c) and (d) of figure 3. In summary the formula of A-type M_2O_3 can be re-written as $(\text{MO})_2\text{O}$, thus emphasizing the different oxide ions in the structure [19].

Besides the aforementioned A-type, two additional types of M_2O_3 are known, shown in figure 2. A-type M_2O_3 is the hexagonal form, stable at high temperatures for the early rare-earth elements and the B-type is the high-temperature monoclinic form for lanthanoids starting from samarium. The cubic C-type is the low temperature form [20].

Figure 2: Phase transformation of the rare-earth oxides with the composition Ln_2O_3 . A, B and C are the stability regions of the equilibrium phases and C^* represents the meta-stable form (taken from [20]).

Figure 3: Comparison of the crystal structures of EuOCl (PbFCl type; a, b [21]) and of A-type Eu_2O_3 (c, d [22]). $[\text{OEu}_4]$ tetrahedra in red, $[\text{OEu}_6]$ octahedron in violet and Cl^- in rose.

1.3 Crystal structure of $\text{Eu}^{\text{III}}_3\text{O}_3(\text{PO}_4)$

In literature only two crystal structure analyses of lanthanoid oxide-phosphates were reported so far. Monoclinic $\text{Nd}^{\text{III}}_3\text{O}_3(\text{PO}_4)$ (SG: Cm (no. 8), $Z = 12$) was synthesized by two groups [23, 24]. The second compound $\text{Eu}^{\text{III}}_3\text{O}_3(\text{PO}_4)$ (SG: $C2/m$ (no. 12), $Z = 12$) was synthesized and characterized by W. Grunwald [3, 25]. The structure of $\text{Eu}^{\text{III}}_3\text{O}_3(\text{PO}_4)$ is given in figure 4. Both lanthanoid oxide-phosphates contain cationic metal oxide layers ${}^2[\text{OLn}_{4/4}]^+$ parallel to (010), with orthophosphate groups $[\text{PO}_4]^{3-}$ located in between the layers. In both compounds the coordination number of the metal atoms varies from six to eight. One noteworthy difference between the structures is, that the lattice parameters of the europium oxide-phosphate are smaller than the lattice parameters of the neodymium oxide-phosphate due to the lanthanoid contraction [26]. Moreover, the europium oxide-phosphate has a twofold rotational axis along the b -axis that leads to a centrosymmetric space group in contrast to the neodymium oxide-phosphate with non-centrosymmetric space group.

The structures of the oxide-phosphates $Ln_3O_3(PO_4)$ are comparable to those of the oxide-chlorides $LnOCl$ which were discussed already. The latter crystallize in the $PbFCl$ structure type as visualized in figure 3a and b. A connection of the anion-centered tetrahedra $[OLn_4]$ along four edges is present in these structures.

Figure 4: Crystal structure of $Eu_3O_3(PO_4)$ projected along the crystallographic b -axis (a) and along the c -axis (b) [3]. $[OEu_4]$ in red and $[PO_4]^{3-}$ in yellow.

1.4 Transition metal phosphates

Among the transition metals, iron is one representative with a huge variety of phosphates. For divalent iron the compounds $Fe^{II}_2P_2O_7$ [27], $Fe^{II}_4O(PO_4)_2$ [28], $Fe^{II}_2(P_4O_{12})$ [29], $Fe^{II}_3(PO_4)_2$ [30] and $Fe^{II}(P_4O_{11})$ [31] are stated in literature. Moreover, phosphates of trivalent iron $Fe^{III}(PO_4)$ [32], $Fe^{III}_3O_3(PO_4)$ [33] and $Fe^{III}_4(P_2O_7)_3$ [34] were synthesized and the crystal structures elucidated. In addition to them, mixed-valent iron phosphates $Fe^{II}Fe^{III}O(PO_4)$ [35], $Fe^{II}_8Fe^{III}O_8(PO_4)$ [36], $Fe^{II}Fe^{III}_2(P_2O_7)_2$ [37], $Fe^{II}_5Fe^{III}_2(P_2O_7)_4$ [38] and $Fe^{II}_3Fe^{III}_4(PO_4)_6$ [39] are reported in literature. The oxide-phosphate $Fe_3O_3(PO_4)$ was solved using single crystal diffraction data. The synthesis was performed with the educts $FePO_4$ and Fe_2O_3 at a temperature of 900 °C. It is of interest, whether the corresponding compounds of cobalt and chromium exist.

In the field of cobalt oxo-salts, the artificial leaf project [40] by Nocera, is a first attempt

of constructing an inexpensive solar-to-fuels system. The system operates with natural water sources at ambient conditions under use of earth-abundant elements. The oxygen evolving complex (OEC) has the function to oxidize water to oxygen. In the artificial leaf, the OEC contains Co-P_i-clusters (P_i = orthophosphate) [40]. The catalytic activity of Co-OEC is provided by a unique self-repair mechanism via oxidation of Co²⁺ (aq) to Co³⁺ (aq) [41]. The cluster contains cobalt, oxygen and phosphate groups as visualized in figure 5.

Figure 5: Structure of the Co-OEC (P_i not shown) (a) and Co-OEC structure rotated by 45° with P_i (b) (adapted from Nocera [40]).

1.5 Aim of this thesis

This thesis aimed to confirm the preparative and crystallographic work of Serra [4] on oxide-phosphates for selected lanthanoid ions (*Ln*: Sm, Eu). Elucidation of their crystal structures was a target. Here, we prioritized development of structural models of Eu₇O₆(PO₄)₃ and Eu₈O₉(PO₄)₂. Moreover, orientating experiments on syntheses for new transition metal oxide-phosphates with chromium and cobalt should be performed in accordance to their lanthanoid oxide-phosphate counterparts.

2 Synthesis

2.1 Lanthanoid oxide-phosphates

The syntheses performed in this work were high-temperature solid state reactions. Therefore, the educts were ground and pressed to a tablet or pellet. The pelletized sample was put into a platinum crucible as reaction vessel. Platinum is used due to its high melting temperature (1768.4 °C [42]) and its inertness. However, the high reaction temperatures led to some evaporation and deposition of platinum crystals on the pellet surface. This is caused by a chemical vapour transport (CVT) following reaction equation 1 with oxygen as transport agent forming volatile PtO_2 in an endothermic process [43]. In literature, temperatures of formation of the volatile species are stated. Schäfer *et al.* give a temperature of 1340 °C [44], Alcock *et al.* a temperature of 1500 °C [45].

The platinum crystals were removed under the microscope with the help of tweezers and scratching. After the annealing the sample was ground again and X-ray powder diffraction pattern were recorded. The various syntheses of the lanthanoid oxide-phosphates are summarized in table 1.

Table 1: Syntheses of lanthanoid oxide-phosphates.

no.	target	educts	m [mg]	n [mmol]	ratio $Ln:P$	T [°C]	t [d]	products ^{c)}
1	EuPO_4	Eu_2O_3 $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{HPO}_4$	1144.0 856.3	3.25 6.48	1:1	a)	a)	EuPO_4
2	SmPO_4	Sm_2O_3 $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{HPO}_4$	1139.1 862.5	3.27 6.53	1:1	a)	a)	SmPO_4
3a	$\text{Eu}_3\text{O}_3(\text{PO}_4)$	Eu_2O_3 EuPO_4	293.4 206.3	0.83 0.84	3:1	1100	7	$\text{Eu}_3\text{O}_3(\text{PO}_4)$
3b	$\text{Eu}_3\text{O}_3(\text{PO}_4)$ ^{b)}	$\text{Eu}_3\text{O}_3(\text{PO}_4)$				1600	3.5	$\text{Eu}_7\text{O}_6(\text{PO}_4)_3$ $\text{Eu}_8\text{O}_9(\text{PO}_4)_2$
4	$\text{Eu}_7\text{O}_6(\text{PO}_4)_3$	Eu_2O_3 EuPO_4	146.1 153.9	0.42 0.62	7:3	1600	1	$\text{Eu}_7\text{O}_6(\text{PO}_4)_3$
5a	$\text{Eu}_8\text{O}_9(\text{PO}_4)_2$	Eu_2O_3 EuPO_4	204.7 95.8	0.58 0.39	4:1	1400	2.5	$\text{Eu}_8\text{O}_9(\text{PO}_4)_2$ B-type Eu_2O_3

Table 1: Continued from previous page.

no.	target	educts	<i>m</i> [mg]	<i>n</i> [mmol]	ratio <i>Ln:P</i>	<i>T</i> [°C]	<i>t</i> [d]	products ^{c)}
5b	Eu ₈ O ₉ (PO ₄) ₂	Eu ₂ O ₃	204.3	0.58	4:1	1600	3.5	Eu ₈ O ₉ (PO ₄) ₂ by-product
		EuPO ₄	95.6	0.38				
5c	Eu ₈ O ₉ (PO ₄) ₂	Eu ₂ O ₃	254.3	0.72	4.8:1	1600	3.5	Eu ₈ O ₉ (PO ₄) ₂ B-type Eu ₂ O ₃ by-product
		EuPO ₄	95.5	0.39				
5d	Eu ₈ O ₉ (PO ₄) ₂	Eu ₂ O ₃	204.2	0.58	3.36:1	1600	3.5	Eu ₈ O ₉ (PO ₄) ₂ Eu ₇ O ₆ (PO ₄) ₃
		EuPO ₄	120.6	0.49				
5e	Eu ₈ O ₉ (PO ₄) ₂	Eu ₂ O ₃	189.3	0.54	3.4:1	1600	3.5	Eu ₈ O ₉ (PO ₄) ₂
		EuPO ₄	110.7	0.45				
6	Sm ₃ O ₃ (PO ₄)	Sm ₂ O ₃	293.5	0.84	3:1	1100	30	Sm ₃ O ₃ (PO ₄)
		SmPO ₄	203.6	0.84				
7a	Sm ₇ O ₆ (PO ₄) ₃	Sm ₂ O ₃	145.9	0.42	7:3	1400	9	Sm ₇ O ₆ (PO ₄) ₃
		SmPO ₄	154.0	0.63				
7b	Sm ₇ O ₆ (PO ₄) ₃	product 7a				1600	3.5	Sm ₇ O ₆ (PO ₄) ₃
8	Sm ₈ O ₉ (PO ₄) ₂	Sm ₂ O ₃	189.1	0.54	3.4:1	1600	3.5	Sm ₈ O ₉ (PO ₄) ₂
		SmPO ₄	110.9	0.45				

^{a)} annealing ramp: 200 °C (1 d), 250 °C (0.5 d), 300 °C (0.5 d), 500 °C (0.5 d) and 1000 °C (1 d). ^{b)} high-temperature form. ^{c)} according to XRPD.

2.2 Oxide-phosphates of transition metals

Adopting the procedure for synthesis of the lanthanoid oxide-phosphates two experiments with chromium compounds were performed (table 2). In the first experiment chromium oxide and chromium phosphate were used to synthesize chromium oxide-phosphate in a solid state reaction. For the second experiment the goal was to see, if chromium phosphate powder decomposes to a chromium oxide-phosphate via thermal degradation. Both experiments were carried out in an open system in air with platinum crucibles as reaction vessels.

For cobalt, a solution combustion synthesis (see section 8.5) with the starting materials listed in table 2 with the aim of synthesizing "Co₃O₃(PO₄)" was performed. The ignition temperature of the gel residue was 400 °C. Afterwards, the finely dispersed powder was

Synthesis

put into a silica crucible ("half ampoule") and annealed in a temperature range between 400 and 1100 °C with steps of 50 °C. After each annealing step, XRPD pattern were recorded. The measurement time was set to 15 minutes or 30 minutes, respectively.

Table 2: Syntheses of transition metal oxide-phosphates.

no.	target	educts	<i>m</i> [mg]	<i>n</i> [mmol]	<i>T</i> [°C]	<i>t</i> [d]	products ^{b)}
9	"Cr ₃ O ₃ (PO ₄)"	Cr ₂ O ₃ CrPO ₄ ^{a)}	152.6 147.6	1.00 1.00	1100	26	Cr ₂ O ₃
10	"Cr ₃ O ₃ (PO ₄)"	CrPO ₄ ^{a)}			1050	6	α-/β-CrPO ₄ Cr ₂ O ₃
11	"Co ₃ O ₃ (PO ₄)"	Co(NO ₃) ₂ · 6 H ₂ O (NH ₄) ₂ HPO ₄ NH ₂ CH ₂ COOH HNO ₃ (65%)	1365.7 206.6 1412.3 ≈ 80 mL	4.69 1.56 18.81	400 750 900 1000 1100	1 5 2 2 4	Co ₃ O ₄ Co ₃ (PO ₄) ₂ Co ₃ O ₄ Co ₃ (PO ₄) ₂ CoO Co ₃ (PO ₄) ₂ CoO Co ₂ (SiO ₄) SiO ₂

^{a)} mixture of α- and β-CrPO₄ (approx. 1:4; see appendix, figure 35). ^{b)} according to XRPD.

3 Thermal decomposition of $Ln_3O_3(PO_4)$ (Ln : Sm, Eu)

To examine the high-temperature stability, syntheses of oxide-phosphates $Ln_3O_3(PO_4)$ were revisited. In this section the results on oxide-phosphates $Ln_3O_3(PO_4)$ (Ln : Sm, Eu) are presented. Observations during the experiments are depicted and later discussed.

3.1 $Eu_3O_3(PO_4)$

$Eu_3O_3(PO_4)$ was reproduced according to the synthetic pathway published in the work of Grunwald [25] and resulted in a pure phase product. The XRPD pattern is shown in figure 6. Moreover, the question whether a high-temperature form of $Eu_3O_3(PO_4)$ exists or whether the compound decomposes at higher temperatures was investigated. Experiment 3b (see table 1) led to the XRPD pattern represented in figure 7. There is no high-temperature form observed, instead thermal decomposition occurred, which is later discussed.

Figure 6: $Eu_3O_3(PO_4)$. IP-Guinier XRPD pattern ($Cu-K_{\alpha 1}$) of experiment no. 3a, table 2 (a). Simulated pattern (b) based on structure data from [25].

Figure 7: IP-Guinier XRPD pattern (Co- $K_{\alpha 1}$) of the high-temperature experiment no. 3b of $Eu_3O_3(PO_4)$ (a). Simulated pattern (b) of $Eu_7O_6(PO_4)_3$ (red, 42.6 wt %) and $Eu_8O_9(PO_4)_2$ (black, 57.4 wt %) based on structure data obtained in this work. The amorphous background was cut off below 2.5° in 4θ .

3.2 $Sm_3O_3(PO_4)$

Synthesis of $Sm_3O_3(PO_4)$ was performed similar to that of $Eu_3O_3(PO_4)$. The XRPD pattern is visualized in figure 8. The lattice parameters of the compound were refined with the program SOS by use of the hkl indices given in the work of Grunwald [25]. The result of the indexing is listed in table 16 in the appendix. Table 3 compares the lattice parameters of this work and those reported by Serra [4].

Table 3: Comparison of the lattice parameters of $Sm_3O_3(PO_4)$ of this work and of literature [4].

$Sm_3O_3(PO_4)$	a [Å]	b [Å]	c [Å]	β [°]	V [Å ³]
this work ^{a)}	12.848(3)	13.008(0)	12.185(9)	108.401(9)	1932.5(0)
literature [4]	12.140	15.840	13.687	108.070	2502.16

^{a)} 13 refl., external standard α - SiO_2 .

Figure 8: $Sm_3O_3(PO_4)$. IP-Guinier powder diffraction pattern ($Cu-K_{\alpha 1}$) of experiment no. 6 (a). Simulated pattern (b), structure model of $Eu_3O_3(PO_4)$ [25] with adjusted lattice parameters.

3.3 Results and discussion

The existence of a high-temperature form of $Eu_3O_3(PO_4)$ was disproved in this work. At a temperature of 1600 °C (3.5 days in air; platinum crucible) $Eu_3O_3(PO_4)$ decomposed completely into $Eu_7O_6(PO_4)_3$ (42.6 wt %) and $Eu_8O_9(PO_4)_2$ (57.4 wt %). One would expect an equal distribution of both compounds. The higher amount of $Eu_8O_9(PO_4)_2$ hints to a different composition than expected containing a higher amount of $EuPO_4$, which is discussed in more detail later in this work. This leads to the conclusion, that $Eu_3O_3(PO_4)$ is stable at 1100 °C and is fully decomposed after 3 days at 1600 °C into the phases $Eu_7O_6(PO_4)_3$ and " $Eu_8O_9(PO_4)_2$ ". Two possible decomposition reactions are shown in equations 2 and 3.

The product phases will be treated in detail in sections 4.1 and 5.1. From neodymium to europium, the lattice parameters of the oxide-phosphates decrease slightly in correlation to the ion radii. This is linked to the lanthanoid contraction that leads to a decrease in ion radius of the lanthanoids in the same manner [26]. This trend is visualized in Table 4.

Table 4: Comparison of the lattice parameters of $Ln_3O_3(PO_4)$ (Ln : Nd, Sm, Eu).

compound	a [Å]	b [Å]	c [Å]	β [°]	V [Å ³]
Nd ₃ O ₃ (PO ₄) [23]	12.966(3)	13.233(5)	12.266(3)	108.66(2)	1994.1(1)
Sm ₃ O ₃ (PO ₄) ^{a)}	12.848(3)	13.008(0)	12.185(9)	108.401(9)	1932.5(0)
Eu ₃ O ₃ (PO ₄) [25]	12.814(1)	12.927(1)	12.141(1)	108.424(2)	1908.0(8)

^{a)} 13 refl., external standard α -SiO₂.

$Pr_3O_3(PO_4)$ 12.970 13.297 12.290 108.50 (PDF-2)

4 Crystallographic characterization of $Ln_7O_6(PO_4)_3$ (Ln : Nd, Sm, Eu)

4.1 Eu₇O₆(PO₄)₃

The synthesis of Eu₇O₆(PO₄)₃ was performed according to experiment no. 4 in table 1. Figure 9 shows the powder diffraction pattern. After development of a structure model, the product was confirmed to be single-phase. The product contained small crystals that were investigated by electron microscopy. Unfortunately, these crystals were too small (length of up to 1 μ m and width of up to 0.6 μ m) for single crystal X-ray diffraction. Consequently, the crystal structure of Eu₇O₆(PO₄)₃ had to be solved on the basis of the powder diffraction data.

Figure 9: Eu₇O₆(PO₄)₃. IP-Guinier powder diffraction pattern (Co-K α_1) of experiment no. 4 (a). Simulation (b) based on the preliminary structure model (see section 4.1.3).

4.1.1 Lattice parameters and space group

In this section, the procedure to determine the lattice parameters and the space group of $Eu_7O_6(PO_4)_3$ is described. The decomposition of the powder diffraction pattern into individual reflections ("peak deconvolution"; 67 reflections) using the built-in routine of Match! [46] was the first step.

After that, the program DICVOL [47] was used to assign the reflections (diffraction angles) to possible unit cells and hkl indices, resulting in the monoclinic cell listed in the appendix (table 17). Interestingly, the lattice parameters obtained here do not match those reported in the literature [4]. The lattice parameter sets are compared in table 5.

Table 5: Comparison of the lattice parameters of $Eu_7O_6(PO_4)_3$ obtained in this work to those reported by Serra [4].

$Eu_7O_6(PO_4)_3$	a [Å]	b [Å]	c [Å]	β [°]	V [Å ³]
DICVOL indexing	12.509(6)	17.790(6)	6.801(8)	100.57(0)	1488.0(8)
literature [4]	20.601	12.315	14.983	119.432	3310.62

The calibration of the diffraction angles on the basis of a measured α -quartz standard powder pattern was performed with the program SOS1 [48]. This procedure had to be done for the Guinier method. For the Debye-Scherrer method it was not necessary to measure a standard due to regular calibration of the device. With the program SOS2 [48] a refinement of the lattice parameters (57 reflections) was carried out. The SOS results are listed in table 18. Electron diffraction confirmed the unit cell derived with DICVOL (see subsequent section 4.1.2).

The volume of the predicted unit cell is $V = 1488.0(8) \text{ \AA}^3$. By comparing the molar volumes of the unit cells of the starting compounds $EuPO_4$ ($V_{\text{mol}} = 69.42 \text{ \AA}^3$ [5]) and Eu_2O_3 (C-type, $V_{\text{mol}} = 80.03 \text{ \AA}^3$ [49]) the molar volume of $Eu_7O_6(PO_4)_3$ was estimated to be $V_{\text{mol}} = 368.32 \text{ \AA}^3$. The volume of the unit cell divided by the estimated molar volume of $Eu_7O_6(PO_4)_3$ resulted in four formula units.

The hkl indices enabled a statement about possible space groups regarding extinctions. The reflection conditions are separated in three classes, namely serial, zonal and integral conditions. The lattice type of the compound is assumed to be primitive. The zonal reflection condition ($h0l$: $h+l = 2n$, 7 reflections) led to an n -gliding plane perpendicular to the b -axis and the serial reflection condition ($0k0$: $k = 2n$, 1 reflection) led to a 2_1 -screw axis along the b -axis. The predicted space group is $P2_1/n$.

4.1.2 Electron diffraction and transmission electron microscopy

The results of electron diffraction and high-resolution transmission electron microscopic studies on $Eu_7O_6(PO_4)_3$ are shown in figures 10, 11 and 12. The measurements confirmed the preliminary unit cell. In figure 13 reflections of diffraction pattern along the a^* - and b^* -axis were indexed. The indexing shows the before mentioned reflection conditions $h0l$: $h + l = 2n$ and $0k0$: $k = 2n$. In figure 13 (b) weak reflections are marked that contradict the former conditions ($h0l$: $h + l = 2n + 1$ and $0k0$: $k = 2n + 1$). However, these reflections are obtained probably due to double diffraction. Therefore, the space group was confirmed by electron diffraction.

Figure 10: $Eu_7O_6(PO_4)_3$. Electron diffraction pattern along $[-1\ 1\ 0]$ (a). Corresponding magnified bright field image of the oblong crystal (b).

Figure 11: $Eu_7O_6(PO_4)_3$. High resolution TEM image along c^* (a). Electron diffraction pattern along c^* (b).

Figure 12: $Eu_7O_6(PO_4)_3$. Electron diffraction pattern of a tilted series along the b^* -axis. Diffraction pattern along $[-1\ 0\ 1]$ (a), along $[-1\ 0\ 2]$ (b), along $[-1\ 0\ 3]$ (c) and along $[-1\ 0\ 4]$ (d).

Figure 13: $Eu_7O_6(PO_4)_3$. Electron diffraction pattern along the b^* -axis (a) and along the a^* -axis (b). Two weak reflections contradicting the space group are marked by green arrows.

4.1.3 Structure model

For the crystal structure solution the direct space approach implemented in the computer program ENDEAVOUR [50] was applied. Therefore, the well resolved powder diffraction pattern (Co- $K_{\alpha 1}$), the proposed lattice parameters and the proposed space group (see section 4.1.1) were used to develop a first structure model. Out of this structure model, the positions of the heavy europium atoms were refined with the software JANA [51]. The phosphate groups were treated as semi-rigid bodies during these calculations. The calculated powder diffraction pattern in comparison to the measured XRPD pattern is represented in figure 14. The R-values of the refinement and the crystallographic data out of the XRPD pattern for $Eu_7O_6(PO_4)_3$ are listed in table 6. Obviously, there is still room for improvement of the structure model. The structure data including the atom positions is listed in table 7.

Figure 14: $Eu_7O_6(PO_4)_3$. IP-Guinier powder diffraction pattern (Co- $K_{\alpha 1}$) (black; a) and calculated pattern of the Rietveld-Refinement (red; a). Difference plot (b).

Table 6: Summary of the crystallographic data and of the Rietveld-Refinement for $Eu_7O_6(PO_4)_3$.

Crystallographic data	SOS	JANA
sum formula	$Eu_7O_6(PO_4)_3$	
crystal system	monoclinic	
space group	$P2_1/n$ (14)	
number of formula units	4	
a [Å]	12.503(0)	12.502(2)
b [Å]	17.775(0)	17.773(2)
c [Å]	6.796(7)	6.798(4)
β [°]	100.56(9)	100.57(1)
cell volume [Å ³]	1484.8(8)	1484.9(9)
structural refinement		
software	JANA [51]	
refinement method	least-squares	
parameters	97	
constraints	46	
weighting scheme	sigma	
R_1 [$I > 3\sigma(I)$]; R_1 (all data) ^{a)}	0.1708; 0.2567	
wR_2 [$I > 3\sigma(I)$]; wR_2 (all data) ^{b)}	0.1526; 0.1591	
R_{exp} ^{c)}	0.0756	
GOF ^{d)}	4.43	

^{a)} $R_1 = (\sum |y_{i,obs} - y_{i,theo}|) / (\sum |y_{i,obs}|)$. ^{b)} $wR_2 = [(\sum w_i |y_{i,obs} - y_{i,theo}|^2) / (\sum w_i (y_{i,obs})^2)]^{1/2}$.
^{c)} $R_{exp} = [(N - P + C) / (\sum w_i (y_{i,obs})^2)]^{1/2}$. ^{d)} $GOF = (wR_2 / R_{exp})^2$.

Table 7: Structure data of $Eu_7O_6(PO_4)_3$.

atom	Wyck.	x	y	z	s.o.f.
O1	4e	0.7311	0.4116	0.1555	1
O2	4e	0.6422	0.5223	0.2831	1
O3	4e	0.5768	0.4769	0.9350	1
O4	4e	0.5420	0.4008	0.2247	1
O5	4e	0.6458	0.3279	0.8500	1
O6	4e	0.6130	0.2785	0.5012	1
O7	4e	0.6631	0.4131	0.5648	1
O8	4e	0.8011	0.3127	0.6681	1
O9	4e	0.4386	0.9626	0.5756	1
O10	4e	0.6259	0.9586	0.7788	1

Table 7: Continued from previous page.

atom	Wyck.	x	y	z	s.o.f.
O11	4e	0.5712	0.8654	0.5051	1
O12	4e	0.5980	1.0	0.4229	1
O13	4e	0.0946	0.3482	0.4511	1
O14	4e	0.3800	0.2631	0.7058	1
O15	4e	0.3420	0.3676	0.1873	1
O16	4e	0.4909	0.2595	0.0858	1
O17	4e	0.7374	0.1471	0.3395	1
O18	4e	0.275	0.36	0.5	1
P1	4e	0.6224	0.4527	0.1488	1
P2	4e	0.6813	0.3334	0.6458	1
P3	4e	0.5587	0.9465	0.5694	1
Eu1	4e	0.0856	0.7658	0.1257	1
Eu2	4e	0.1823	0.2475	0.6679	1
Eu3	4e	0.6453	0.0492	0.1340	1
Eu4	4e	0.1343	0.3561	0.1163	1
Eu5	4e	0.0834	0.6617	0.6138	1
Eu6	4e	0.5768	0.6248	0.0921	1
Eu7	4e	0.1120	0.9644	0.1104	1

4.1.4 Description and discussion of the crystal structure

The preliminary structure model of $Eu_7O_6(PO_4)_3$ depicted in figure 15 consists of corrugated layers of edge sharing tetrahedra $[OEu_4]$ and one octahedron $[OEu_6]$. The preferred coordination between neighboring tetrahedra is via edges. The connection between tetrahedra and adjacent octahedra is via shared faces. The connected $[OEu_n]$ polyhedra form a 2D layer parallel to the a,c -plane with the composition $[Eu_7O_6]^{9+}$. The space between two layers is occupied by orthophosphate groups $[PO_4]^{3-}$. The europium ions are coordinated to oxide ions of the anion centered polyhedra and to oxide ions of the orthophosphate groups. The coordination number of the europium atoms varies between six and eight, as visualized with the corresponding distances $d(Eu-O)$ in figure 16 and listed in table 8.

The metal oxide sub-structure shows some similarity to the CeO_2 structure type and to the related structures of A- and C-type Eu_2O_3 . In contrast, the metal oxide layers differ markedly from those of the oxide-phosphates $Ln_3O_3(PO_4)$. The cause of this difference lies in the connectivity of the metal oxide tetrahedra. As in A-type Eu_2O_3 the tetrahedra are connected via three edges, whereas for $Ln_3O_3(PO_4)$ they are connected via four

edges. The basis framework of the structures is the fluorite structure type. Braunite (SG: $I4_1/acd$ (no. 142), $Z = 8$) [52] is a derivative structure of fluorite with ordered anion voids forming a network of $[OMn_4]$ tetrahedra connected to neighboring tetrahedra via three edges. The resulting holes are filled by isolated $[SiO_4]^{4-}$ tetrahedra comparable to $Eu_7O_6(PO_4)_3$. Moreover, CeO_2 (SG: $Fm\bar{3}m$ (no. 225), $Z = 4$) [53] crystallizing in the fluorite structure can be transformed from the cubic into the hexagonal crystal system (SG: $R\bar{3}m$ (no. 166), $Z = 3$). From there, by adding one additional atom at the position $(0, 0, 1/2)$ a layered structure motif with resemblance to the $[Eu_7O_6]^{9+}$ layers can be achieved. The newly added ion is the central ion of the anion centered octahedra and manually disabling the graphical output of oxide ions in a regular manner led to the comparable structure motif.

The preliminary structure model of $Eu_7O_6(PO_4)_3$ contains small crystallochemical inconsistencies. To mention is that the P-P distance between orthophosphate groups with the central atom P3 is too small, $d(P3-P3) = 2.4806 \text{ \AA}$. Moreover, the oxygen atoms (O9 and O12) between these orthophosphate groups are too close together, with an interatomic distance of 0.8081 \AA .

Figure 15: $Eu_7O_6(PO_4)_3$. Preliminary structure model projected along the crystallographic c -axis (a) and along the b -axis (b). $[PO_4]^{3-}$ tetrahedra in yellow, $[OEu_4]$ tetrahedra in red and $[OEu_6]$ octahedra in violet.

Figure 16: $Eu_7O_6(PO_4)_3$. Ball-and-stick representation [54] of the coordination spheres $[EuO_n]$ ($n = 6, 7, 8$) around the Eu^{3+} ions.

Table 8: Interatomic distances [\AA] of $Eu_7O_6(PO_4)_3$.

[Eu1O ₇]	^{a)}	[Eu2O ₈]	^{a)}	[Eu3O ₇]	^{a)}	[Eu4O ₈]	^{a)}
O8	2.277(7)	O17	2.247(6)	O13	2.232(8)	O9	2.382(8)
O15	2.299(6)	O16	2.358(4)	O12	2.323(0)	O13	2.421(0)
O16	2.337(0)	O13	2.446(7)	O17	2.390(8)	O17	2.469(3)
O14	2.371(2)	O14	2.453(6)	O9	2.408(3)	O6	2.516(4)
O11	2.467(5)	O5	2.542(4)	O18	2.570(8)	O11	2.556(2)
O6	2.484(7)	O6	2.611(4)	O2	2.655(9)	O15	2.560(3)
O18	2.667(5)	O18	2.670(4)	O10	2.875(1)	O18	2.866(9)
		O1	2.897(2)			O12	2.873(2)
[Eu5O ₆]	^{a)}	[Eu6O ₈]	^{a)}	[Eu7O ₆]	^{a)}		
O14	2.180(5)	O2	2.298(9)	O15	2.211(5)		
O13	2.195(2)	O15	2.316(2)	O7	2.306(2)		
O16	2.294(3)	O17	2.317(3)	O2	2.336(6)		
O8	2.642(1)	O14	2.423(8)	O18	2.528(2)		
O11	2.735(2)	O4	2.424(4)	O3	2.550(9)		
O1	2.864(0)	O16	2.455(9)	O4	2.651(7)		
		O3	2.619(4)				
		O3	2.836(8)				
[P1O ₄]		[P2O ₄]		[P3O ₄]			
O4	1.522(1)	O7	1.521(2)	O12	1.522(1)		
O3	1.523(0)	O8	1.522(4)	O11	1.522(5)		
O2	1.530(3)	O6	1.529(9)	O10	1.529(9)		
O1	1.535(4)	O5	1.536(0)	O9	1.536(6)		

^{a)} cut-off distance of 3 \AA .

4.2 $Sm_7O_6(PO_4)_3$ and $Nd_7O_6(PO_4)_3$

The oxide-phosphate $Sm_7O_6(PO_4)_3$ was synthesized at a temperature of 1400 °C and the powder diffraction pattern is visualized in figure 17. Using the crystal structure data of $Eu_7O_6(PO_4)_3$, the lattice parameters of the samarium compound were refined with the program SOS. The result is listed in table 9.

Figure 17: $Sm_7O_6(PO_4)_3$. IP-Guinier powder diffraction pattern (Cu- $K_{\alpha 1}$) of experiment no. 7a (a). Simulation (b) based on the preliminary structure model of $Eu_7O_6(PO_4)_3$ (see section 4.1.3).

In comparison to $Eu_7O_6(PO_4)_3$ that was synthesized at 1600 °C as pure phase, the samarium relative develops an additional reflection with relative intensity of 50 above a temperature of 1400 °C that is not explained by the structure model. The corresponding powder diffraction pattern is visualized in figure 38 in the appendix.

In literature Serra reported on $Nd_7O_6(PO_4)_3$ and its powder diffraction pattern [4]. The pattern and a corresponding simulation are compared in figure 18. The simulation is performed on the basis of the structure model of $Eu_7O_6(PO_4)_3$ stated in section 4.1.3. The lattice parameters were refined with the program SOS with hkl indices taken from $Eu_7O_6(PO_4)_3$. The simulation describes the reported powder pattern reasonably well.

Figure 18: $Nd_7O_6(PO_4)_3$. Powder diffraction pattern reported by Serra *et al.* [4] (a). Simulated powder diffraction pattern (b).

4.3 Results and discussion

In literature, Serra *et al.* stated that the composition $Ln_7O_6(PO_4)_3$ is possible for the lanthanoids La to Tb [4]. For the lanthanoids europium and samarium the synthesis of $Ln_7O_6(PO_4)_3$ was confirmed in this work. The lattice parameters stated in literature do not match our findings. A preliminary crystal structure model has been derived from the powder diffraction data. Full refinement was not yet successful. To complete the structure model of $Eu_7O_6(PO_4)_3$ synchrotron diffraction data with better resolution is required.

$Sm_7O_6(PO_4)_3$, isotypic to $Eu_7O_6(PO_4)_3$ was prepared under similar conditions at 1400 °C and was determined to be single-phase. Table 9 represents the lattice parameters of the different $Ln_7O_6(PO_4)_3$ compounds stated in this work. As expected, the lattice parameters decrease slightly from neodymium to europium explainable through the lanthanoid contraction [26].

Table 9: Comparison of the lattice parameters of $Ln_7O_6(PO_4)_3$ (Ln : Nd, Sm, Eu).

compound	a [Å]	b [Å]	c [Å]	β [°]	V [Å ³]
Nd ₇ O ₆ (PO ₄) ₃ ^{a)}	12.747(8)	17.838(7)	6.964(3)	100.475(1)	1557.3(2)
Sm ₇ O ₆ (PO ₄) ₃ ^{b)}	12.585(0)	17.819(1)	6.853(5)	100.397(6)	1511.6(8)
Eu ₇ O ₆ (PO ₄) ₃	12.502(2)	17.773(2)	6.798(4)	100.571(0)	1484.9(9)

^{a)} 24 refl. from literature. ^{b)} 23 refl., external standard α -SiO₂.

5 Crystallographic characterization of $Ln_8O_9(PO_4)_2$ (Ln : Sm, Eu, Gd)

5.1 Eu₈O₉(PO₄)₂

The existence of Eu₈O₉(PO₄)₂ was examined. Moreover, setting up a structure model of the compound was a main target.

Different synthesis pathways were chosen and performed by varying the heating temperature and the ratio between the educts as listed in table 1 (experiments 5a to 5e).

Figure 19 shows representative powder diffraction pattern obtained during the experiments. The first powder diffraction pattern (a) corresponds to a stoichiometric amount of educts, that means a ratio of 2 : 3 (EuPO₄ : Eu₂O₃) which was mixed and annealed at a temperature of 1400 °C. While synthesizing the expected product phase, monoclinic B-type Eu₂O₃ was still present.

As a second experiment the same educt ratio was annealed at 1600 °C. Interestingly, a by-phase was formed at that temperature with no detectable amount of Eu₂O₃ left. In the appendix in figure 36 the powder diffraction pattern is visualized.

In a third experiment, the amount of Eu₂O₃ as an educt was increased to a ratio of 1 : 1.9 (EuPO₄ : Eu₂O₃). Thereby, it was tested, if Eu₂O₃ would remain unreacted in the product phase, or whether the unknown by-phase of experiment 5b is promoted. Both were detected in the product phase besides Eu₈O₉(PO₄)₂. In the appendix in figure 37 the corresponding powder diffraction pattern is visualized.

Furthermore, the amount of EuPO₄ was increased to a ratio of 5 : 5.9 (EuPO₄ : Eu₂O₃) in another experiment. The powder diffraction pattern is presented in figure 19 (b) and contains some amount of Eu₇O₆(PO₄)₃ as product besides Eu₈O₉(PO₄)₃.

A synthesis with the ratio 5 : 6 (EuPO₄ : Eu₂O₃) was performed containing no detectable by-phase and is shown in (c).

In (d) the simulated powder diffraction pattern according to the preliminary structure model of Eu₈O₉(PO₄)₂ (see section 5.1.1) is visualized.

Figure 19: $Eu_8O_9(PO_4)_2$. IP-Guinier powder diffraction pattern (Cu-K α_1) at 1400 °C, B-type Eu_2O_3 [55] (green arrows), experiment no. 5a (a). At 1600 °C and higher educt amount of $EuPO_4$, $Eu_7O_6(PO_4)_3$ (red arrows), experiment no. 5d (b). Educt ratio 5 : 6 ($EuPO_4 : Eu_2O_3$) at 1600 °C, experiment no. 5e (c). Simulation according to the preliminary structure model (d). In (b) and (c) the amorphous background is cut off below 10° in 2θ .

5.1.1 Lattice parameters, space group and structure model

The procedure out of section 4.1.1 for $Eu_7O_6(PO_4)_3$ to determine the lattice parameters and the space group was adapted for $Eu_8O_9(PO_4)_2$. The DICVOL calculations with 46

reflections resulted in two monoclinic unit cells, which can be recognized as different unit cell settings of the same structure. In literature, Serra [4] stated lattice parameters for $Eu_8O_9(PO_4)_2$ which differ from those received in this work. In table 10 the different lattice parameters of the literature, DICVOL calculation and those refined with SOS are listed. The second unit cell suggestion was chosen for further investigation. All main reflections are explained by the cell determined with DICVOL. In the paper of Serra electron diffraction was performed to determine a unit cell. The b parameter of their measurement matches our result. The preliminary unit cell needs to be confirmed by electron diffraction experiments, which are pending. For the indexing the serial reflection condition ($0k0$: $k = 2n$) led to an 2_1 -screw axis along the b -axis. For further calculations the common monoclinic space group $P2_1/m$ was assumed.

For the crystal structure solution the direct space approach implemented in the software ENDEAVOUR [50] was applied as was described for $Eu_7O_6(PO_4)_3$.

Table 10: Comparison of the lattice parameters of $Eu_8O_9(PO_4)_2$ obtained in this work to those reported by Serra [4].

$Eu_8O_9(PO_4)_2$	a [Å]	b [Å]	c [Å]	β [°]	V [Å ³]
1. indexing ^{a)}	19.519(0)	10.885(7)	6.782(9)	109.240(0)	1360.7(2)
2. indexing ^{a)}	18.458(4)	10.881(0)	6.786(4)	91.050(0)	1362.7(9)
refined indexing ^{b)}	18.449(6)	10.880(5)	6.787(2)	91.051(0)	1362.2(6)
literature [4]	20.398	10.873	14.149	114.724	2850.41

^{a)} DICVOL. ^{b)} 42 refl.

5.1.2 Description and discussion of the crystal structure

The structure model of $Eu_8O_9(PO_4)_2$ is shown in figure 20. It consists of edge sharing $[OEu_4]$ tetrahedra. The polyhedra are assumed to span a 3D network with the composition $[Eu_8O_9]^{6+}$. Unfortunately, the structure shows strong crystallochemical inconsistencies so that this feature is not developed in total. For instance, the oxide ions of the orthophosphates are not positioned crystallochemically correct. Therefore, only the phosphorus atoms are visualized. As a reference, CeO_2 [53] was projected onto the distorted monoclinic unit cell of $Eu_8O_9(PO_4)_2$. Looking at a 2D layer of the oxide sub-structure of CeO_2 consisting of $[OCe_4]$ tetrahedra, each tetrahedron is sharing three edges with neighboring tetrahedra, comparable to A-type Eu_2O_3 . The $Eu_8O_9(PO_4)_2$ metal oxide sub-structure shares this motif in parts. However, the structure contains holes where some $[OEu_4]$ tetrahedra are replaced by isolated orthophosphate groups. By creating artificial ordered anion vacancies of oxide ions from the 3D reference structure, similar holes can be obtained, which strengthens the structural relation of the models. The structure data is listed in table 11.

Figure 20: $Eu_8O_9(PO_4)_2$. Preliminary structure model projected along the crystallographic c -axis (a) and along the b -axis (b). [OEu₄] tetrahedra in red, phosphorus atoms in yellow and the europium atoms in teal. The oxygen atom positions need further refinement, for that reason they are not shown.

Table 11: Structure data of $Eu_8O_9(PO_4)_2$.

atom	Wyck.	x	y	z	s.o.f.
O1	4f	0.11641	0.63547	0.82962	0.5
O2	4f	0.06090	0.59148	0.42040	0.333
O3	2e	0.00588	0.75	0.9244	1
O4	2e	0.4705	0.25	0.625	1
O5	2e	0.5872	0.25	0.6719	1
O6	4f	0.47632	0.16184	0.83612	1
O7	4f	0.76093	-0.07826	0.42450	1
O8	2e	0.36841	0.25	0.76255	1
O9	4f	0.69420	0.13619	0.53549	1
O10	2e	0.29917	0.75	0.0242	1
O11	4f	0.62002	0.12921	0.25380	1
O12	2e	0.4862	0.25	0.39539	1
O13	4f	0.68487	0.55439	0.02983	1
O14	4f	0.13048	0.05891	0.25699	1
O15	2e	0.3005	0.25	0.43239	1
O16	2e	0.0361	0.25	0.14667	1
O17	2e	0.75198	0.25	0.3125	1
O18	2e	0.82261	0.25	0.02924	1
O19	2e	0.115	0.25	0.72	1
O20	2e	0.46395	0.25	0.1089	1
O21	2e	0.70311	0.75	0.6	1
P1	2e	0.08832	0.75	0.93615	1
P2	2e	0.5172	0.25	0.7725	1
Eu1	4f	0.16654	0.60003	0.44955	1
Eu2	2e	0.18983	0.25	0.40964	1
Eu3	2e	0.35505	0.25	0.09413	1
Eu4	4f	0.34007	0.08080	0.58872	1
Eu5	4f	0.00786	0.08334	0.25406	1
Eu6	4f	0.17694	0.07108	0.92462	1
Eu7	2e	0.00692	0.25	0.73898	1
Eu8	4f	0.48526	0.01569	0.26918	1

5.1.3 A further structure model

For a further structure solution attempt the direct space approach implemented in the program ENDEAVOUR [50] was again applied. Now, the unit cell out of the DICVOL

calculation and space group $P2_1/c$ were used. The structure model is shown in figure 21 with the corresponding structure data listed in table 12. This structure model of $Eu_8O_9(PO_4)_2$ also consists of edge sharing $[OEu_4]$ tetrahedra that are assumed to span a 3D network with ordered vacancies. The difference between these structure models is the different positioning of the phosphate groups. All in all, both structure models show similar structure motifs.

Figure 21: $Eu_8O_9(PO_4)_2$. Second structure model projected along the crystallographic c -axis (a) and along the b -axis (b). $[OEu_4]$ tetrahedra in red, phosphorus atoms in yellow and the europium atoms in teal. The oxygen atom positions need further refinement, for that reason they are not shown.

Table 12: Structure data of the second $Eu_8O_9(PO_4)_2$ approach.

atom	Wyck.	x	y	z	s.o.f.
O1	4e	0.8839	0.6704	0.5137	1
O2	4e	0.4924	0.253	0.6902	1
O3	4e	0.04	0	0.17	1
O4	4e	0.2172	0.4936	0.3477	1
O5	4e	0.6997	0.2171	0.9688	1
O6	4e	0.6518	0.0046	0.9306	1
O7	4e	0.589	0.1526	0.1493	1
O8	4e	0.5831	0.1802	0.7847	1
O9	4e	0.6409	0.7863	0.0251	1
O10	4e	0.6235	0.5602	0.9977	1
O11	4e	0.7376	0.6554	0.8803	1
O12	4e	0.7135	0.6442	0.2402	1
O13	4e	0.7811	0.3361	0.135	1
P1	4e	0.32	0.1614	0.35	1
Eu1	4e	0.505	0.84	0	0.5
Eu2	4e	0.8515	0.8424	0.3337	1
Eu3	4e	0.1767	0.8353	0.645	1
Eu4	2d	0.5	0	0.5	1
Eu5	2c	0	0	0.5	1
Eu6	4e	0.3348	0.8743	0.3526	1
Eu7	4e	178	0.4795	0.6683	1
Eu8	4e	0.3394	0.4724	0.3094	1
Eu9	4e	0.012	0.6735	0.4689	1

5.2 $Sm_8O_9(PO_4)_2$ and $Gd_8O_9(PO_4)_2$

Complementary to experiment 5e (table 1) $Sm_8O_9(PO_4)_2$ was synthesized. The powder diffraction pattern is shown in figure 22. The simulation was performed on the basis of the lattice parameters refined with SOS and the structure model of $Eu_8O_9(PO_4)_2$ (see section 5.1.1). The indexing is listed in the appendix (table 23). The simulated powder diffraction pattern matches the measured pattern in almost every reflection. There are differences in the intensities between the simulation and the experimental pattern. Especially for the reflections of the simulation at 9.5° and 26° in 4θ where no measured reflection is visible. In literature lattice parameters of $Sm_8O_9(PO_4)_2$ are stated [4]. Table 13 lists the lattice parameters of the literature and the result of our SOS refinement. Except for the b -value different lattice parameters were obtained.

The powder diffraction pattern of $Gd_8O_9(PO_4)_2$ from Serra [4] and the simulated powder diffraction pattern based on the structure model of $Eu_8O_9(PO_4)_2$ are compared in figure 23. Table 13 lists the lattice parameters refined with the program SOS and the ones stated by Serra [4]. The lattice parameters of literature and those of our simulation are different.

Figure 22: $Sm_8O_9(PO_4)_2$. IP-Guinier powder diffraction pattern ($Cu-K_{\alpha 1}$) of experiment no. 8 (a). The simulation (b) based on the preliminary structure model of $Eu_8O_9(PO_4)_2$ (see section 5.1.1).

Table 13: Comparison of the lattice parameters of $Ln_8O_9(PO_4)_2$ (Ln : Sm,Gd) of this work and of literature [4].

$Sm_8O_9(PO_4)_2$	a [Å]	b [Å]	c [Å]	β [°]	V [Å ³]
this work ^{a)}	18.583(5)	10.944(8)	6.833(2)	91.106(7)	1389.5(6)
literature [4]	20.461	10.908	14.224	114.838	2880.98
$Gd_8O_9(PO_4)_2$	a [Å]	b [Å]	c [Å]	β [°]	V [Å ³]
this work ^{b)}	18.431(2)	10.865(2)	6.782(8)	91.382(4)	1357.9(2)
literature [4]	20.352	10.854	14.105	114.710	2830.51

^{a)} 14 refl., external standard α -SiO₂. ^{b)} 11 refl. from literature.

Figure 23: $Gd_8O_9(PO_4)_2$. Powder diffraction pattern of the literature [4] (a). Simulated powder diffraction pattern (b).

5.3 Results and discussion

In literature, Serra *et al.* stated the oxide-phosphate $Ln_8O_9(PO_4)_2$ possible for the lanthanoids Sm to Lu [4].

For the lanthanoids europium and samarium the synthesis of $Ln_8O_9(PO_4)_2$ was confirmed in this work. Comparable to $Ln_7O_6(PO_4)_3$ the lattice parameters for these lanthanoid oxide-phosphates do not match those stated by Serra. TEM measurements are still pending to confirm our unit cell. While the unit cell reported by Serra is different to the one derived in this study, the agreement of the b -axis via electron diffraction and

the match to d values obtained by Serra support our indexing. As for $Eu_7O_6(PO_4)_3$ the preliminary structure model shows close relation to the fluorite structure of CeO_2 . Indeed, the reported unit cell is related to the cubic fluorite unit cell ($Z = 4$) by transforming the latter with the transformation matrix $\begin{pmatrix} 2 & 0 & -1 \\ 2 & -3/2 & 1/2 \\ 2 & 3/2 & 1/2 \end{pmatrix}$ resulting in a number of formula units of $Z = 36$.

It is assumed that in the 3D network of $Eu_8O_9(PO_4)_2$ $[PO_4]^{3-}$ substitutes $[EuO_3]^{3-}$ or $(P-O)^{3+}$ substitutes Eu^{3+} in an ordered manner. There is an uncertainty regarding the composition of $Ln_8O_9(PO_4)_2$, resulting out of the performed experiments (see section 5.1). A stoichiometric approach for $Eu_8O_9(PO_4)_2$ led to B-type Eu_2O_3 remaining in the product, whereas the 5 : 6 ($EuPO_4$: Eu_2O_3) approach was confirmed to be single-phase after development of the structure model. The preliminary crystal structure has been derived out of the powder diffraction data. Synchrotron diffraction data with better resolution is required to improve the structure model of $Eu_8O_9(PO_4)_2$.

$Sm_8O_9(PO_4)_2$, isotypic to $Eu_8O_9(PO_4)_2$ was prepared under similar conditions and was determined to be single-phase as well (5 : 6, $SmPO_4$: Sm_2O_3). All lattice parameters of $Ln_8O_9(PO_4)_2$ are compared in table 14. The trend of smaller lattice parameters for the heavier lanthanoid ion is as expected and can be explained by the lanthanoid contraction [26].

Table 14: Comparison of the lattice parameters of $Ln_8O_9(PO_4)_2$ (Ln : Sm, Eu, Gd).

compound	a [Å]	b [Å]	c [Å]	β [°]	V [Å ³]
$Sm_8O_9(PO_4)_2$	18.583(5)	10.944(8)	6.833(2)	91.106(7)	1389.5(6)
$Eu_8O_9(PO_4)_2$	18.458(4)	10.881(0)	6.786(4)	91.050(0)	1362.7(9)
$Gd_8O_9(PO_4)_2$	18.431(2)	10.865(2)	6.782(8)	91.382(4)	1357.9(2)

6 Oxide-phosphates of transition metals

6.1 " $\text{Cr}^{\text{III}}_3\text{O}_3(\text{PO}_4)$ " and " $\text{Co}^{\text{III}}_3\text{O}_3(\text{PO}_4)$ "

Figure 24 depicts the powder diffraction pattern for the chromium experiments 9 and 10 in table 2. The powder diffraction pattern (a) and the corresponding line chart (b) point out, that only chromium oxide was formed during the heating process at 1100 °C.

The powder diffraction pattern (c) with the corresponding line chart (d) confirmed, that at 1050 °C the educts ($\alpha\text{-CrPO}_4$ and $\beta\text{-CrPO}_4$) were still present in the product. Noteworthy, the product also contained chromium oxide Cr_2O_3 .

Figure 25 represents the XRPD pattern of " $\text{Co}^{\text{III}}_3\text{O}_3(\text{PO}_4)$ " after different tempering steps for experiment 11 in table 2. After ignition of the gel the product contained two phases, namely cobalt oxide (Co_3O_4) and cobalt phosphate ($\text{Co}_3(\text{PO}_4)_2$). After the annealing steps the reflections got sharper, due to better crystallinity of the products. At a heating temperature of 900 °C, the color of the product changed from dark brown to violet. At a temperature between 900 °C and 1000 °C, the oxides CoO and Co_3O_4 were both present in the product phase. At 1000 °C, the whole Co_3O_4 decomposed into CoO .

At the highest chosen temperature of 1100 °C the product color changed to blue. There the cobalt compounds reacted with the SiO_2 of the ampoule by forming $\text{Co}_2(\text{SiO}_4)$. Moreover the sample contained a high amount of silicon dioxide in two modifications, namely the low temperature α -cristobalite and α -quartz.

6.2 Results and discussion

In this section, the experiments for chromium oxide-phosphate " $\text{Cr}_3\text{O}_3(\text{PO}_4)$ " and cobalt oxide-phosphate " $\text{Co}_3\text{O}_3(\text{PO}_4)$ " are discussed.

For chromium a thermal degradation reaction took place in both conducted experiments. The existence of " $\text{Cr}_3\text{O}_3(\text{PO}_4)$ " could therefore not be proven. The corresponding decomposition equilibrium is visualized in equation 4.

With our set up, at 1050 °C, CrPO_4 partially started to decompose. At higher temperature (1100 °C) the whole CrPO_4 thermally degraded.

The annealing steps after the SCS of the cobalt compounds resulted in two products. Cobalt oxides Co_3O_4 , the low temperature oxide, and CoO , the high-temperature oxide were formed [56]. Between 900 and 1000 °C both oxides coexist under air. Additionally, the decomposition of Co_3O_4 into CoO takes place rather slowly and at these temperatures

longer heating rates would result in a fully decomposition to CoO. In this work the formation of $\text{Co}_2(\text{SiO}_4)$ occurred at around $1100\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ due to the wrong choice of reaction vessel. A product with the composition " $\text{Co}_3\text{O}_3(\text{PO}_4)$ " was not synthesized. For further investigations, another reaction vessel like a platinum crucible has to be used.

Figure 24: " $\text{Cr}^{\text{III}}_3\text{O}_3(\text{PO}_4)$ ". IP-Guinier powder diffraction pattern ($\text{Cu-K}\alpha_1$) of the products of experiment no. 9 (a) and of experiment no. 10 (c). Simulation of Cr_2O_3 in black after Finger *et al.* [57] (b). Simulations of α -chromium orthophosphate (α - CrPO_4 , red) [58] and β -chromium orthophosphate (β - CrPO_4 , green) [59] and chromium oxide (Cr_2O_3) (d).

Figure 25: " $\text{Co}^{\text{III}}_3\text{O}_3(\text{PO}_4)$ ". IP-Guinier XRPD pattern ($\text{Cu-K}\alpha_1$) after ignition at 400 °C (a), after annealing at 750 °C (b), at 900 °C (c), at 1000 °C (d) and at 1100 °C (e). Reference pattern $\text{Co}_3(\text{PO}_4)_2$ [60] (light blue), Co_3O_4 [61] (red), CoO [62] (green), SiO_2 α -cristobalite [63] (rose), SiO_2 α -quartz [64] (violet) and $\text{Co}_2(\text{SiO}_4)$ [65] (dark blue).

7 Summary and outlook

The general goals of this work were the syntheses of selected lanthanoid and transition metal oxide-phosphates. Moreover, solving the crystal structures of $\text{Eu}_7\text{O}_6(\text{PO}_4)_3$ and $\text{Eu}_8\text{O}_9(\text{PO}_4)_2$ were targets.

The experiments in this thesis confirm the existence of oxide-phosphates with compositions $\text{Ln}_3\text{O}_3(\text{PO}_4)$ and $\text{Ln}_7\text{O}_6(\text{PO}_4)_3$ for Ln : Nd, Sm and Eu. $\text{Eu}_3\text{O}_3(\text{PO}_4)$ decomposes at 1600 °C to $\text{Eu}_7\text{O}_6(\text{PO}_4)_3$ and " $\text{Eu}_8\text{O}_9(\text{PO}_4)_2$ ". Similar experiments suggest for " $\text{Ln}_8\text{O}_9(\text{PO}_4)_2$ " (Ln : Sm, Eu and Gd) a slightly higher phosphate content and the approximate formula $\text{Ln}_{14}\text{O}_{15}(\text{PO}_4)_4$. The compositional diagram for the europium oxide-phosphates adapted to the results of the experiments in this work is shown in figure 26.

Figure 26: Compositional diagram of the Eu_2O_3 - EuPO_4 system. The hatched line represents the suggested composition " $\text{Eu}_8\text{O}_9(\text{PO}_4)_2$ " reported in literature [4].

For $\text{Eu}_7\text{O}_6(\text{PO}_4)_3$ the synthesis of Serra [4] was confirmed. The unit cell derived in this work differs from the one given in literature. However, TEM measurements confirm our unit cell. The preliminary structure model was constructed out of powder diffraction data and contains layers built from $[\text{OEu}_4]$ tetrahedra and $[\text{OEu}_6]$ octahedra separated by orthophosphate groups as structural motif. The results are summarized in figure 27. The model shows slight crystallochemical inconsistencies that have to be improved in future work. In a different approach DFT calculations for structure optimization might be applied.

Figure 27: $\text{Eu}_7\text{O}_6(\text{PO}_4)_3$. Left: IP-Guinier powder diffraction pattern (Co- $K_{\alpha 1}$; a) and simulated pattern based on the preliminary structure model (b). Right: Preliminary structure model. $[\text{PO}_4]^{3-}$ yellow, $[\text{OEu}_4]$ red and $[\text{OEu}_6]$ violet.

$\text{Sm}_7\text{O}_6(\text{PO}_4)_3$ was synthesized and the corresponding lattice parameters and those of $\text{Nd}_7\text{O}_6(\text{PO}_4)_3$ on the basis of the powder pattern stated in literature [4] were refined under use of the preliminary structure model of $\text{Eu}_7\text{O}_6(\text{PO}_4)_3$. Thus, the samarium and neodymium compounds were confirmed to be isotypic to $\text{Eu}_7\text{O}_6(\text{PO}_4)_3$.

X-ray powder diffraction by Serra for " $\text{Eu}_8\text{O}_9(\text{PO}_4)_2$ " is confirmed, yet indexing led to a different monoclinic unit cell. The structure model for " $\text{Eu}_8\text{O}_9(\text{PO}_4)_2$ " is in agreement with the anticipated slightly higher phosphate content. The structure model for " $\text{Eu}_8\text{O}_9(\text{PO}_4)_2$ ", as the one for $\text{Eu}_7\text{O}_6(\text{PO}_4)_3$ is related to the fluorite structure family with the occasional substitution of $[\text{EuO}_3]^{3-}$ by $[\text{PO}_4]^{3-}$ or Eu^{3+} by $(\text{P}-\text{O})^{3+}$. The 3D ordering for this substitution, which should be similar to the incorporation of $[\text{SiO}_4]^{4-}$ tetrahedra into MnO_2 in the Braunite structure type still has to be unveiled.

" $\text{Sm}_8\text{O}_9(\text{PO}_4)_2$ ", isotypic to " $\text{Eu}_8\text{O}_9(\text{PO}_4)_2$ " was synthesized under similar conditions. The unit cells of " $\text{Sm}_8\text{O}_9(\text{PO}_4)_2$ " and " $\text{Gd}_8\text{O}_9(\text{PO}_4)_2$ " out of this work fit well into the row of lanthanoid oxide-phosphates.

For summary, synchrotron diffraction data is needed to improve the synthesized samarium and europium oxide-phosphate structure models. Serra stated that the lanthanoids from terbium to lutetium are able to form an additional oxide-phosphate with the composition $\text{Ln}_{12}\text{O}_{15}(\text{PO}_4)_2$. Terbium is the most promising candidate for future experiments. Serra stated that terbium is capable of forming all mentioned oxide-phosphates making it the only lanthanoid forming four different oxide-phosphates.

The transition metal oxide-phosphates " $\text{Cr}_3\text{O}_3(\text{PO}_4)$ " and " $\text{Co}_3\text{O}_3(\text{PO}_4)$ " could not be synthesized in this work.

8 Preparative methods

8.1 Preparation of pellets

To avoid undesired by-products that form by reaction between the crucible and the reactants it is of importance to pelletize the powder via a mechanical press. As a positive side effect it speeds up the solid state reaction by increasing the contact areas between the reactants. In this work, the educts were ground in an agate mortar and afterwards filled into a pressing mold by the help of a funnel. Depending on the amount of educts, different pressing molds were used. The schematic drawing in figure 28 represents the hydraulic press and the pellet mold used for less than 200 mg substance. In addition to this mold, one mold to form small tablets (200 to 500 mg powder) with a diameter of 7 mm and a height of around 2 mm and one mold to form larger tablets (> 500 mg powder) with a diameter of 12 mm and a height of 3 to 8 mm were used. The pressure to form the pellets amounted to 20-25 kN. The pressing was repeated three times for each sample to guarantee a compact pellet.

Figure 28: Schematic drawing of the hydraulic press used in this work (adapted from [25]). The pressing mold consists of eight parts numbered in this image. 1 to 5 represent the pressing mold and 6 the stamp. Moreover, the encasement is visualized by the numbers 7 and 8.

8.2 Furnaces

During the experiments different furnaces were used. Chamber furnaces NABERTHERM type *L 5/12* with controller *B 170* or *B 180* with maximum heating temperatures of 1200 °C were used for reactions up to 1100 °C. Moreover, for the high-temperature syntheses one zone furnaces were used which reach temperatures up to 1400 °C. For even higher temperatures up to 1600 °C a furnace NABERTHERM type *LHT 04/18* was used. The upper temperature limit of that furnace is 1800 °C. The temperature uncertainty of all mentioned furnaces is approximately ± 25 °C.

8.3 Starting materials

For the syntheses of the oxide-phosphates several starting materials were used. All of them are commercially available and are listed in table 15. Starting with the commercially available educts, precursors for the oxide-phosphate reactions were synthesized.

Table 15: Starting materials used in this study.

chemical	formula	supplier	purity
euprium(III) oxide	Eu_2O_3	Acros Organics	99.99 %
samarium(III) oxide	Sm_2O_3	Alfa	99.9 %
diammonium hydrogen phosphate	$(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{HPO}_4$	Acros Organics	99 + %
chromium(III) oxide	Cr_2O_3	abcr	99.00 %
cobalt(II) nitrate hexahydrate	$\text{Co}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6 \text{H}_2\text{O}$	Honeywell	98 %
glycine	$\text{NH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{COOH}$	Labochem	p. a.
nitric acid (65 %)	HNO_3	Riedel-de Haën	p. a.
α -/ β -chromium orthophosphate ^{a)}	CrPO_4		

^{a)} substance was synthesized by a member of the group.

8.4 Solid state reactions

Most syntheses in this work are based on solid state reactions between two or more solid reactants. Solid state reactions have a slow reaction speed compared to gases or liquids due to the inhibited mobility of the atoms or ions in the solid phase [66]. Diffusion speeds to let the reaction happen between two solids have to be nearly 0.6 of the diffusion speed of the product at melting temperature [67]. By increasing the reaction temperature, the atom-/ion-diffusion speed is increased. This is of relevance when some product phase is already formed and the educts have to diffuse through the product phase to react. Figure 29 represents the diffusion process. Moreover, grinding of the educts to get them well distributed in combination with pelletizing the powder to decrease the reaction pathways speed up the reaction process [67].

Figure 29: Schematic drawing of a solid state reaction between $\text{Eu}^{\text{III}}(\text{PO}_4)$ and $\text{Eu}^{\text{III}}_2\text{O}_3$ (adapted from [25]). The arrows show possible diffusion pathways of the educts through the product phase $\text{Eu}^{\text{III}}_3\text{O}_3(\text{PO}_4)$.

8.5 Solution combustion synthesis (SCS)

Combustion synthesis (CS) with its variations is an important method of preparing nanoscale materials. The specific self-sustained thermal process used in this work is called solution combustion synthesis (SCS). The initial components of the SCS are mixed in aqueous solution on a molecular level. The required metal precursors are mixed with glycine acting as fuel, chelating ligand and reductant. Moreover, nitric acid as oxidizing agent is added. Additionally, diammonium hydrogen phosphate ($(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{HPO}_4$) acting as a phosphate source is added to the mixture. The solution is heated up to 80 °C until a gel forms that consists out of a fuel-metal-network. After that, the combustion is initiated at a temperature of 400 °C. The fuel starts to burn and is oxidized. The experiment has to be performed in an open container, because high evolution of gas arises due to formation of N_2 , CO_2 , and H_2O . The high gasification leads to an expansion of the solid product and a rapid decrease of temperature after the reaction, which leads to a finely dispersed product. In figure 30 the three main steps of the solution combustion synthesis are visualized [68, 69].

Figure 30: Schematic description of the three main steps in the solution combustion synthesis (taken from [69]).

9 Analytical methods

The samples, synthesized in this work have been characterized via different methods. X-ray powder diffractometry was performed with the Guinier method and the Debye-Scherrer method. Furthermore, transmission electron microscopy was carried out.

9.1 X-ray powder diffraction (XRPD)

Crystals are homogeneous, anisotropic solid states, whose building blocks are strictly three-dimensional, periodically ordered [70]. The smallest motif of a crystal is the unit cell that forms the crystal lattice by translation in all three spatial directions. The net planes containing the atoms of the translational lattice can be indexed with the miller indices. Interatomic distances in a crystal are in the range of 1 to 3 Å. X-ray radiation has nearly the same range of wavelengths which leads to interference between the waves and the lattice. The process in which the X-ray radiation interferes with matter is called X-ray diffraction. In the process the wavelength is not altered but the X-rays are deflected in all three spatial directions. X-rays with the wavelength λ diffract at the lattice planes of the crystals, where the angle of incidence θ_i is equal to the angle of reflection θ . Interference between the waves that are reflected at different lattice planes with the distances d_{hkl} arises. The reflection of the waves at different planes leads to constructive interference if the path difference fulfills the Bragg equation 5 schematically visualized in figure 31.

$$2d \sin \theta = n\lambda \quad (n = 1, 2, 3, \dots) \quad (5)$$

The angle between the incident beam and the reflected beam is the angle of diffraction 2θ . Each crystal has different lattice planes with the corresponding miller indices (hkl) and therefore each crystal has a unique diffraction pattern [71].

Figure 31: Schematic drawing of the beam path of X-rays fulfilling the Bragg's reflection condition (adapted from [25]).

9.1.1 Guinier method

The Imaging Plate-technology (IP) is used in the Guinier X-ray diffraction method. A diffractometer HUBER *G670* with $\text{Cu-K}\alpha_1$ radiation of a wavelength λ of 1.54059 \AA was used (acceleration voltage: 40 kV and current: 30 mA). The apparatus and the beam path are shown in figure 32. The sample has to be ground and applied onto an X-ray amorphous foil and afterwards dispersed in acetone or ethanol on a sample holder. After evaporation of the dispersion liquid, the sample holder can be inserted into the diffractometer. The radiation is generated in an X-ray tube with a Cu-anode and then directed through a germanium single crystal (100) that monochromatizes the X-rays. The X-rays passing directly through the sample are absorbed by a primary beam stop. An X-ray sensitive film, the so called Imaging Plate, detects the diffracted radiation. The plate is coated with bariumbromidefluoride (BaBrF) doped with Eu^{2+} ions. During the exposure time, the X-rays induce an oxidation from Eu^{2+} to Eu^{3+} . A red laser scanner scans the Imaging Plate and induces a recombination of the color centers by forming Eu^{2+} ions and emitting photons of the wavelength of blue light. The intensity of the emitted light is measured by a photomultiplier and leads to the diffraction pattern [71].

Figure 32: Schematic drawing of the beam path in a Guinier camera (adapted from [25]).

9.1.2 Debye-Scherrer method

Some of the powder diffraction pattern in this work were recorded with a Debye-Scherrer camera. The Debye-Scherrer camera is equipped with a MYTHEN-detector (STOE Stadi P PSD, Co-K $_{\alpha 1}$ -radiation $\lambda = 1.788965 \text{ \AA}$) and with a germanium single crystal as monochromator (net plane (111)).

The preparation of the sample requires a finely ground powder, that is applied onto a sample holder, equipped with an X-ray amorphous foil. Onto the powder a second foil is attached. The sample is placed vertically to the X-ray beam and is rotated during the measurement to obtain an averaged powder pattern over many crystals. Due to the statistical distribution of the crystal orientation in the powder, the Bragg condition is fulfilled [71].

The MYTHEN-detector is moving in a circular manner around the rotating sample to generate the powder pattern. The microstrip detector contains silicon sensors, each having 1280 strips with a length of 8 mm on a pitch of 50 μm . The sensor thickness is 300 μm . The radiation impinging the sensor leads to electrical charging of the sensor, which can be read out by a computer chip [72]. The powder diffraction pattern are recorded for several hours in steps of 800 s for every 0.015° in 2θ .

The powder diffraction pattern were imported into the phase identification software MATCH! [46]. With this software the experimental data was compared to the crystallographic databases PDF-2 [73] and ICSD [1]. For the graphical representation, the experimental data was saved in the .dat-format and transformed into a vector graphic (.wmf-file) with the help of the program ORIGINPro 8G [74]. Line charts of the powder diffraction pattern were calculated with LAZY PULVERIX [75] and GINA [76]. The required crystal structure data was taken from ICSD-entries [1] or from the preliminary structure models. With the software CorelDRAW 2018 [77] the graphical processing of the powder diffraction pattern and the corresponding line charts was performed.

9.2 Rietveld method

Rietveld refinement is a method to refine crystal structures. The precondition is a starting model of the crystal structure containing the most important features of the actual structure, for example approximately correct positions of the heavy atoms. Isotypical compounds can be used as starting models due to their close relation to the desired structure. In this work the structure models of the different compounds were obtained in a direct space approach implemented in the software ENDEAVOUR [50, 78]. Optimally, the refinement is performed with single crystal data. Without single crystal data, a good resolved powder diffraction pattern of the pure sample is required.

Single crystal measurements facilitate the obtaining of structure factors of each lattice

plane. In particular if the lattice planes lie very close together. The problem of powder diffraction data is the overlay of such reflections with loss of information. The Rietveld method solves this problem mathematically by extrapolating the powder diffraction pattern as a function of the diffraction angle. The shape of the reflections are best described by the Pseudo-Voigt-function although there are several other mathematical approaches [79].

The Rietveld calculations were performed with the program JANA2006 [51]. First, a Le Bail fit was performed to simulate the experimental powder diffraction pattern. Therefore, the background points, the zero point, the cell parameters and the asymmetric parameters were fitted to simulate the experimental powder pattern. After that, the refinement of the crystal structure was started. Constraints were applied to optimize the crystal structure. These constraints were used to form rigid bodies, like PO_4 -groups. Moreover, restraints were used to define distances and angles between atoms to reach a meaningful crystal structure. Furthermore, the isotropic displacement parameters could have been adjusted [71]. However, this was not possible regarding our structure.

The quality of the refinement is rated in R-values. Besides the R-values, a difference plot of the experimental powder diffraction pattern against the calculated powder diffraction pattern indicates the goodness of the refinement. The ideal difference plot would be a straight line, so that the calculated pattern does not deviate from the experimental pattern, which can not be achieved in practice.

9.3 Transmission electron microscopy (TEM)

Transmission electron microscopy (TEM) is used as a high resolution imaging technique to observe materials. The incident electron beam is accelerated in vacuum and parallelized by several condenser lenses before reaching the sample. Electrons transmitted through the sample, that has to be thin enough to be passed by electrons, are focused by lenses and collected by a parallel detector to create an image. The electron diffraction can be recorded in the back focal plane of the objective lens and is magnified. This method gives insights into the crystal structure of the specimen, in essence lattice parameters or crystal orientations [80].

A transmission electron microscope Philips-FEI *CM30T* was used. It is equipped with an MSC-CCD camera and operates with an accelerating voltage of 300 kV [81]. The sample is placed on a copper mesh coated with a graphite foil by dispersion in ethanol.

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10 Appendix

10.1 XRPD pattern

Figure 33: EuPO_4 . IP-Guinier XRPD pattern ($\text{Cu-K}\alpha_1$) of experiment no. 1 (precursor; a). Simulated pattern [82] (b).

Figure 34: SmPO_4 . IP-Guinier XRPD pattern ($\text{Cu-K}\alpha_1$) of experiment no. 2 (precursor; a). Simulated pattern [82] (b).

Figure 35: CrPO₄. IP-Guinier XRPD pattern (Cu-K _{α 1}; a). Simulated pattern (b) of α -CrPO₄ [58] in red and β -CrPO₄ [59] in green.

Figure 36: Eu₈O₉(PO₄)₂. IP-Guinier XRPD pattern (Cu-K _{α 1}) of experiment no. 5b (a). Simulated pattern (b). The unknown by-phase reflections are marked by green stars.

Figure 37: Eu $_8$ O $_9$ (PO $_4$) $_2$. IP-Guinier XRPD pattern (Cu-K α_1) of experiment no. 5c (a). Simulated pattern of Eu $_8$ O $_9$ (PO $_4$) $_2$ and B-type Eu $_2$ O $_3$ [55] (b). The unknown by-phase reflection with the highest intensity is marked by a red star.

Figure 38: Sm $_7$ O $_6$ (PO $_4$) $_3$. IP-Guinier XRPD pattern (Cu-K α_1) of experiment no. 7b at 1600 °C (a). Simulated pattern (b). An unknown reflection is marked by a red star.

10.2 Indexing of XRPD pattern

Table 16: $\text{Sm}_3\text{O}_3(\text{PO}_4)$. Indexing of the XRPD pattern (Cu- $\text{K}\alpha_1$) with the observed and theoretical diffraction angles of 13 reflections.

h	k	l	$4\Theta_{\text{exp.}} [^\circ]$	$4\Theta_{\text{theo.}} [^\circ]$	$\Delta^{\text{a)}}$	$I_{\text{exp.}}^{\text{b)}}$	$I_{\text{theo.}}^{\text{b)}}$	$d_{\text{theo.}} [\text{\AA}]$
0	2	0	27.115	27.206	0.09	302	666	6.5040
0	0	2	30.552	30.625	0.08	22	45	5.7814
1	1	-3	45.819	45.834	0.02	295	311	3.8773
3	3	0	60.204	60.227	0.05	1000	1000	2.9651
4	0	-3	62.221	62.224	0.01	417	393	2.8722
4	2	-3	68.174	68.190	0.04	66	64	2.6274
0	4	3	72.248	72.213	0.09	19	26	2.4855
3	5	0	82.273	82.327	0.15	110	100	2.1911
0	6	0	83.272	83.244	0.08	78	166	2.1680
2	4	3	83.831	83.836	0.02	97	98	2.1534
6	0	0	89.123	89.108	0.05	160	183	2.0319
4	6	-3	105.733	105.728	0.02	159	162	1.7304
7	3	-3	109.466	109.461	0.02	251	126	1.6757

a) $\Delta = |\sin^2 \Theta_{\text{theo.}} - \sin^2 \Theta_{\text{exp.}}| \cdot 1000$. b) I_{max} is normalized to 1000.

Table 17: $\text{Eu}_7\text{O}_6(\text{PO}_4)_3$. Indexing of the XRPD pattern (Co- $\text{K}\alpha_1$) ($a = 12.5096 \text{ \AA}$, $b = 17.7906 \text{ \AA}$, $c = 6.8018 \text{ \AA}$ and $\beta = 100.570^\circ$) with observed and calculated diffraction angles of 67 reflections. The indexing was performed with the program DICVOL [47].

h	k	l	$4\Theta_{\text{exp.}} [^\circ]$	$4\Theta_{\text{theo.}} [^\circ]$	$\Delta^{\text{a)}}$	$I_{\text{exp.}}^{\text{b)}}$	$d_{\text{theo.}} [\text{\AA}]$
1	1	0	20.26	20.30	0.04	38	10.116
0	2	0	23.08	23.08	0.00	47	8.895
1	2	0	28.50	28.52	0.02	314	7.207
1	0	-1	32.20	32.20	0.00	39	6.386
2	0	0	33.46	33.46	0.00	10	6.149
1	1	-1	34.20	34.24	0.04	28	6.011
2	1	0	35.40	35.42	0.02	44	5.811
0	2	1	38.56	38.54	0.02	101	5.345
2	1	-1	42.78	42.78	0.00	11	4.819
1	2	1	44.26	44.28	0.02	10	4.659
0	3	1	46.52	46.52	0.00	63	4.437
2	3	0	48.38	48.38	0.00	25	4.268
1	4	0	49.40	49.40	0.00	56	4.183
1	3	1	51.42	51.42	0.00	26	4.020

Table 17: Continued from previous page.

h	k	l	$4\Theta_{\text{exp.}} [^\circ]$	$4\Theta_{\text{theo.}} [^\circ]$	$\Delta^{\text{a)}}$	$I_{\text{exp.}}^{\text{b)}}$	$d_{\text{theo.}} [\text{\AA}]$
3	1	0	51.76	51.76	0.00	11	3.994
2	2	1	54.90	54.90	0.00	16	3.769
3	2	0	55.60	55.60	0.00	42	3.723
0	4	1	55.92	55.90	0.02	53	3.703
2	4	0	57.48	57.48	0.00	31	3.604
1	4	1	60.10	60.10	0.00	103	3.450
2	3	1	60.90	60.90	0.00	36	3.406
3	3	0	61.54	61.54	0.00	9	3.372
0	0	2	62.08	62.08	0.00	3	3.343
1	1	-2	62.40	62.38	0.02	10	3.327
3	0	1	64.10	64.10	0.00	13	3.240
2	0	-2	65.08	65.06	0.02	858	3.193
0	5	1	66.16	66.18	0.02	120	3.141
1	5	-1	66.90	66.90	0.00	21	3.108
4	0	0	67.66	67.66	0.00	314	3.074
4	1	0	68.70	68.70	0.00	468	3.029
3	4	0	69.06	69.06	0.00	42	3.014
1	5	1	69.82	69.82	0.00	1000	2.982
1	2	2	71.48	71.46	0.02	40	2.916
3	4	-1	71.90	71.90	0.00	193	2.898
4	2	-1	73.12	73.12	0.00	13	2.852
3	3	1	73.34	73.34	0.00	17	2.843
2	0	2	76.40	76.38	0.02	193	2.734
3	2	-2	76.72	76.70	0.02	50	2.723
2	1	2	77.32	77.32	0.00	128	2.702
4	3	-1	77.86	77.86	0.00	41	2.685
2	6	0	78.26	78.26	0.00	9	2.671
3	5	-1	80.38	80.36	0.02	282	2.604
3	3	-2	81.28	81.26	0.02	20	2.576
1	4	2	82.66	82.64	0.02	7	2.535
4	4	-1	84.12	84.10	0.02	4	2.493
2	3	2	84.48	84.46	0.02	5	2.483
0	5	2	86.18	86.16	0.02	12	2.436
3	4	-2	87.32	87.30	0.02	7	2.410
4	3	1	87.76	87.76	0.00	9	2.394
3	2	2	91.40	91.38	0.02	5	2.304

Table 17: Continued from previous page.

h	k	l	$4\Theta_{\text{exp.}} [^\circ]$	$4\Theta_{\text{theo.}} [^\circ]$	$\Delta^{\text{a)}}$	$I_{\text{exp.}}^{\text{b)}}$	$d_{\text{theo.}} [\text{\AA}]$
5	3	0	92.76	92.74	0.02	54	2.271
4	4	1	93.48	93.46	0.02	13	2.255
0	6	2	95.14	95.12	0.02	56	2.218
3	6	1	96.56	96.56	0.00	42	2.187
-2	6	2	97.26	97.24	0.02	10	2.173
-2	2	3	97.68	97.68	0.00	28	2.164
5	4	0	98.26	98.22	0.04	10	2.152
-1	3	3	99.96	99.94	0.02	37	2.118
1	1	3	100.32	100.30	0.02	34	2.111
4	5	1	100.46	100.42	0.04	46	2.108
-2	3	3	101.50	101.48	0.02	70	2.088
4	5	-2	103.64	103.62	0.02	48	2.047
0	7	2	104.98	104.96	0.02	17	2.023
6	2	-1	105.42	105.42	0.00	5	2.015
1	3	3	106.24	106.20	0.04	7	2.001
-1	5	3	111.60	111.56	0.04	315	1.912
0	5	3	113.08	113.06	0.02	26	1.889

^{a)} $\Delta = |4\Theta_{\text{theo.}} - 4\Theta_{\text{exp.}}|$. ^{b)} I_{max} is normalized to 1000.

Table 18: $\text{Eu}_7\text{O}_6(\text{PO}_4)_3$. Indexing of the XRPD pattern (Co- $\text{K}\alpha_1$) with the observed and theoretical diffraction angles of 57 reflections.

h	k	l	$4\Theta_{\text{exp.}} [^\circ]$	$4\Theta_{\text{theo.}} [^\circ]$	$\Delta^{\text{a)}}$	$I_{\text{exp.}}^{\text{b)}}$	$I_{\text{theo.}}^{\text{b)}}$	$d_{\text{theo.}} [\text{\AA}]$
1	1	0	20.274	20.305	0.02	38	1	10.1094
0	2	0	23.093	23.105	0.01	47	50	8.8875
1	2	0	28.511	28.538	0.03	314	254	7.2019
1	0	-1	32.210	32.229	0.02	39	36	6.3818
1	1	-1	34.210	34.258	0.06	28	2	6.0064
2	1	0	35.410	35.437	0.04	44	16	5.8081
0	2	1	38.570	38.567	0.00	101	23	5.3406
2	1	-1	42.790	42.813	0.04	11	3	4.8163
1	2	1	44.270	44.314	0.07	10	2	4.6550
0	3	1	46.531	46.564	0.06	63	27	4.4330
2	3	0	48.391	48.421	0.05	25	2	4.2654
1	4	0	49.411	49.437	0.05	56	52	4.1790
1	3	1	51.432	51.465	0.06	26	35	4.0170

Table 18: Continued from previous page.

h	k	l	$4\Theta_{\text{exp.}} [^\circ]$	$4\Theta_{\text{theo.}} [^\circ]$	$\Delta^{\text{a)}}$	$I_{\text{exp.}}^{\text{b)}}$	$I_{\text{theo.}}^{\text{b)}}$	$d_{\text{theo.}} [\text{\AA}]$
3	1	0	51.772	51.789	0.03	11	6	3.9923
2	2	1	54.913	54.946	0.07	16	28	3.7669
3	2	0	55.613	55.643	0.06	42	47	3.7207
0	4	1	55.933	55.958	0.05	53	43	3.7001
2	4	0	57.494	57.532	0.08	31	6	3.6010
1	4	1	60.115	60.149	0.07	103	134	3.4477
2	3	1	60.916	60.938	0.05	36	34	3.4040
3	3	0	61.556	61.573	0.04	9	6	3.3698
0	0	2	62.097	62.123	0.06	3	2	3.3407
3	0	1	64.118	64.146	0.07	13	4	3.2380
2	0	-2	65.098	65.118	0.05	858	722	3.1909
2	1	-2	66.179	66.188	0.02	120	83	3.1407
1	5	-1	66.920	66.957	0.09	21	5	3.1057
4	0	0	67.680	67.697	0.04	314	335	3.0727
4	1	0	68.721	68.732	0.03	468	355	3.0278
3	4	0	69.081	69.101	0.05	42	17	3.0121
1	5	1	69.842	69.872	0.07	1000	1000	2.9799
1	2	2	71.503	71.521	0.05	40	44	2.9134
1	6	0	72.404	72.377	0.07	12	1	2.8800
4	2	-1	73.144	73.164	0.05	13	5	2.8501
3	3	1	73.364	73.397	0.09	17	2	2.8414
2	0	2	76.427	76.438	0.03	193	229	2.7323
3	2	-2	76.747	76.760	0.03	50	36	2.7213
2	1	2	77.348	77.372	0.06	128	134	2.7066
4	3	-1	77.888	77.903	0.04	41	32	2.6829
3	5	-1	80.411	80.427	0.04	282	484	2.6020
3	3	-2	81.312	81.320	0.02	20	20	2.5746
1	4	2	82.693	82.700	0.02	7	11	2.5335
4	4	-1	84.155	84.157	0.01	4	14	2.4916
2	3	2	84.515	84.526	0.03	5	1	2.4812
3	4	-2	87.358	87.372	0.04	7	17	2.4041
0	7	1	88.540	88.553	0.04	32	34	2.3736
3	6	-1	89.861	89.866	0.01	24	52	2.3407
4	4	1	93.526	93.523	0.01	13	9	2.2540
0	6	2	95.188	95.203	0.05	56	8	2.2165
3	6	1	96.610	96.629	0.06	42	0	2.1857

Table 18: Continued from previous page.

h	k	l	$4\Theta_{\text{exp.}} [^\circ]$	$4\Theta_{\text{theo.}} [^\circ]$	$\Delta^{\text{a)}}$	$I_{\text{exp.}}^{\text{b)}}$	$I_{\text{theo.}}^{\text{b)}}$	$d_{\text{theo.}} [\text{\AA}]$
2	6	-2	97.311	97.323	0.04	10	2	2.1711
1	3	-3	100.015	100.020	0.02	37	30	2.1161
4	5	1	100.516	100.497	0.06	46	44	2.1067
2	3	-3	101.558	101.558	0.00	70	43	2.0862
6	2	-1	105.484	105.478	0.02	5	1	2.0139
1	3	3	106.305	106.294	0.04	7	0	1.9995
1	5	-3	111.674	111.664	0.03	315	417	1.9106
0	5	3	113.157	113.161	0.02	26	13	1.8873

a) $\Delta = |\sin^2 \Theta_{\text{theo.}} - \sin^2 \Theta_{\text{exp.}}| \cdot 1000$. b) I_{max} is normalized to 1000.

Table 19: $\text{Sm}_7\text{O}_6(\text{PO}_4)_3$. Indexing of the XRPD pattern (Cu- $\text{K}\alpha_1$) with the observed and theoretical diffraction angles of 23 reflections.

h	k	l	$4\Theta_{\text{exp.}} [^\circ]$	$4\Theta_{\text{theo.}} [^\circ]$	$\Delta^{\text{a)}}$	$I_{\text{exp.}}^{\text{b)}}$	$I_{\text{theo.}}^{\text{b)}}$	$d_{\text{theo.}} [\text{\AA}]$
1	1	0	17.270	17.381	0.07	34	1	10.1662
0	2	0	19.606	19.838	0.17	36	52	8.9096
1	2	0	24.398	24.459	0.06	217	257	7.2312
1	3	0	33.024	33.079	0.07	66	32	5.3551
0	3	1	39.793	39.812	0.03	67	29	4.4565
1	4	0	42.329	42.356	0.04	58	53	4.1916
1	3	1	43.986	43.941	0.07	65	36	4.0421
1	4	1	51.354	51.363	0.02	113	134	3.4658
2	3	1	51.953	51.943	0.02	51	35	3.4278
3	3	0	52.612	52.553	0.11	25	6	3.3887
2	0	-2	55.447	55.472	0.05	741	727	3.2136
2	1	-2	56.405	56.385	0.04	88	83	3.1626
4	0	0	57.623	57.651	0.06	296	336	3.0946
4	1	0	58.502	58.533	0.07	530	358	3.0490
1	5	1	59.620	59.642	0.05	1000	1000	2.9935
3	4	-1	61.377	61.413	0.08	249	137	2.9092
2	0	2	64.871	64.862	0.02	248	234	2.7583
2	1	2	65.630	65.656	0.06	174	136	2.7258
4	3	-1	66.389	66.376	0.03	63	33	2.6971

Appendix

Table 19: Continued from previous page.

h	k	l	$4\Theta_{\text{exp.}}$ [°]	$4\Theta_{\text{theo.}}$ [°]	$\Delta^{\text{a)}}$	$I_{\text{exp.}}^{\text{b)}}$	$I_{\text{theo.}}^{\text{b)}}$	$d_{\text{theo.}}$ [Å]
3	5	-1	68.565	68.587	0.05	383	484	2.6126
5	4	1	91.985	91.973	0.04	287	194	1.9719
1	9	0	92.824	92.810	0.04	73	67	1.9551
6	1	-2	95.160	95.151	0.03	153	179	1.9096

a) $\Delta = |\sin^2 \Theta_{\text{theo.}} - \sin^2 \Theta_{\text{exp.}}| \cdot 1000$. b) I_{max} is normalized to 1000.

Table 20: $\text{Nd}_7\text{O}_6(\text{PO}_4)_3$. Indexing of the powder diffraction pattern [4] with the values out of literature and theoretical diffraction angles of 24 reflections.

h	k	l	$4\Theta_{\text{lit.}}$ [°]	$4\Theta_{\text{theo.}}$ [°]	$\Delta^{\text{a)}}$	$I_{\text{lit.}}^{\text{b)}}$	$I_{\text{theo.}}^{\text{b)}}$	$d_{\text{theo.}}$ [Å]
0	2	0	19.693	19.816	0.09	40	51	8.9193
1	2	0	24.312	24.336	0.02	180	242	7.2674
1	0	-1	27.191	27.096	0.10	20	36	6.5301
1	1	-1	28.890	28.864	0.03	20	1	6.1321
2	1	0	29.910	29.938	0.03	30	14	5.9133
1	3	0	32.929	32.972	0.05	70	30	5.3724
1	2	1	37.268	37.402	0.19	10	2	4.7408
0	3	1	39.528	39.513	0.02	50	29	4.4899
2	3	0	41.087	41.143	0.09	30	2	4.3138
1	4	0	42.287	42.253	0.05	40	51	4.2017
1	3	1	43.547	43.577	0.05	70	36	4.0755
0	4	1	47.546	47.578	0.06	80	44	3.7371
2	4	0	49.005	48.952	0.10	40	6	3.6337
1	4	1	51.005	51.033	0.05	140	134	3.4878
3	3	0	52.065	52.083	0.03	20	6	3.4188
2	4	-1	53.024	53.013	0.02	30	8	3.3598
3	0	1	53.824	53.835	0.02	20	4	3.3094
0	2	2	55.904	55.772	0.27	80	8	3.1966
2	4	1	57.943	57.962	0.04	550	47	3.0783
1	5	1	59.323	59.338	0.03	1000	1000	3.0085
2	5	-1	61.143	61.069	0.16	250	66	2.9252
2	0	2	63.902	63.906	0.01	200	235	2.7985
2	1	2	64.762	64.709	0.12	160	138	2.7647
0	4	2	65.862	65.903	0.10	60	19	2.7159

a) $\Delta = |\sin^2 \Theta_{\text{theo.}} - \sin^2 \Theta_{\text{exp.}}| \cdot 1000$. b) I_{max} is normalized to 1000.

Table 21: $\text{Eu}_8\text{O}_9(\text{PO}_4)_2$. Indexing of the XRPD pattern (Co- $\text{K}\alpha_1$) ($a = 18.4584 \text{ \AA}$, $b = 10.8810 \text{ \AA}$, $c = 6.7864 \text{ \AA}$ and $\beta = 91.050^\circ$) with observed and calculated diffraction angles of 46 reflections. The indexing was performed with the program DICVOL [47].

h	k	l	$4\Theta_{\text{exp.}} [^\circ]$	$4\Theta_{\text{theo.}} [^\circ]$	$\Delta^{\text{a)}$	$I_{\text{exp.}}^{\text{b)}$	$d_{\text{theo.}} [\text{\AA}]$
1	1	0	21.88	21.90	0.02	153	9.376
2	0	0	22.24	22.24	0.00	54	9.229
2	1	0	29.18	29.20	0.02	100	7.040
1	0	-1	32.12	32.10	0.02	9	6.407
1	1	-1	37.26	37.28	0.02	49	5.522
1	1	1	37.62	37.62	0.00	9	5.473
0	2	0	37.84	37.84	0.00	11	5.443
3	1	0	38.42	38.46	0.04	12	5.356
1	2	0	39.44	39.46	0.02	30	5.220
2	1	-1	41.88	41.90	0.02	4	4.920
2	1	1	42.50	42.50	0.00	3	4.852
2	2	0	43.98	44.00	0.02	11	4.688
4	0	0	44.70	44.70	0.00	17	4.615
3	0	1	45.66	45.68	0.00	7	4.517
4	1	0	48.62	48.62	0.00	12	4.249
3	1	-1	48.74	48.74	0.00	14	4.238
1	2	1	50.06	50.06	0.00	132	4.127
3	2	0	50.68	50.70	0.02	7	4.077
2	2	1	53.88	53.88	0.00	30	3.840
4	1	-1	57.08	57.08	0.00	4	3.629
4	1	1	57.98	57.98	0.00	12	3.574
1	3	0	58.22	58.20	0.02	13	3.560
4	2	0	58.90	58.88	0.02	3	3.520
3	2	1	59.64	59.64	0.00	94	3.476
0	0	2	61.08	61.14	0.06	1	3.397
2	3	0	61.44	61.44	0.00	23	3.377
-1	0	2	62.00	61.98	0.02	2	3.348
0	3	1	64.84	64.94	0.10	848	3.120
-1	3	1	65.86	65.84	0.02	18	3.157
1	3	1	66.04	66.02	0.02	272	3.148
5	1	-1	66.48	66.42	0.06	19	3.130
4	2	1	66.94	66.94	0.00	11	3.107
2	1	-2	67.62	67.68	0.06	695	3.073
5	2	0	68.18	68.10	0.08	13	3.055

Table 21: Continued from previous page.

h	k	l	$4\Theta_{\text{exp.}} [^\circ]$	$4\Theta_{\text{theo.}} [^\circ]$	$\Delta^{\text{a)}}$	$I_{\text{exp.}}^{\text{b)}}$	$d_{\text{theo.}} [\text{\AA}]$
2	3	-1	68.64	68.64	0.00	35	3.031
2	3	1	69.04	69.04	0.00	1000	3.015
6	1	0	70.34	70.34	0.00	101	2.961
3	1	-2	72.18	72.18	0.00	47	2.887
1	2	-2	73.20	73.12	0.08	154	2.852
3	3	1	73.74	73.74	0.00	179	2.829
5	2	-1	74.48	74.46	0.02	110	2.802
2	2	2	76.34	76.32	0.02	20	2.737
4	0	2	77.10	77.10	0.00	347	2.710
4	1	-2	78.20	78.18	0.02	26	2.673
7	1	0	81.72	81.70	0.02	30	2.563
5	3	-1	86.48	86.46	0.02	51	2.428

^{a)} $\Delta = |4\Theta_{\text{theo.}} - 4\Theta_{\text{exp.}}|$. ^{b)} I_{max} is normalized to 1000.

Table 22: $\text{Eu}_8\text{O}_9(\text{PO}_4)_2$. Indexing of the XRPD pattern (Co- $\text{K}\alpha_1$) with the observed and theoretical diffraction angles of 42 reflections.

h	k	l	$4\Theta_{\text{exp.}} [^\circ]$	$4\Theta_{\text{theo.}} [^\circ]$	$\Delta^{\text{a)}}$	$I_{\text{exp.}}^{\text{b)}}$	$I_{\text{theo.}}^{\text{b)}}$	$d_{\text{theo.}} [\text{\AA}]$
1	1	0	21.893	21.908	0.01	153	450	9.3717
2	0	0	22.253	22.261	0.01	54	48	9.2233
2	1	0	29.191	29.217	0.03	100	103	7.0356
1	0	-1	32.130	32.101	0.04	9	0	6.4070
1	1	-1	37.270	37.296	0.04	49	2	5.5209
1	1	1	37.630	37.631	0.00	9	9	5.4723
0	2	0	37.850	37.854	0.01	11	12	5.4403
3	1	0	38.430	38.476	0.07	12	2	5.3532
1	2	0	39.450	39.482	0.05	30	17	5.2181
2	1	-1	41.890	41.910	0.03	4	8	4.9188
2	1	1	42.510	42.507	0.00	3	9	4.8505
2	2	0	43.990	44.019	0.05	11	11	4.6859
4	0	0	44.710	44.737	0.04	17	26	4.6116
3	0	1	45.670	45.701	0.05	7	3	4.5155
4	1	0	48.631	48.645	0.03	12	2	4.2460
3	1	-1	48.751	48.763	0.02	14	0	4.2359
1	2	1	50.071	50.080	0.02	132	136	4.1262
3	2	0	50.692	50.727	0.07	7	120	4.0744

Table 22: Continued from previous page.

h	k	l	$4\Theta_{\text{exp.}} [^\circ]$	$4\Theta_{\text{theo.}} [^\circ]$	$\Delta^{\text{a)}}$	$I_{\text{exp.}}^{\text{b)}}$	$I_{\text{theo.}}^{\text{b)}}$	$d_{\text{theo.}} [\text{\AA}]$
2	2	1	53.893	53.892	0.00	30	33	3.8392
4	1	-1	57.094	57.108	0.03	4	35	3.6271
4	1	1	57.994	58.001	0.01	12	25	3.5725
1	3	0	58.235	58.230	0.01	13	7	3.5587
4	2	0	58.915	58.922	0.02	3	6	3.5178
3	2	1	59.655	59.672	0.04	94	146	3.4746
0	0	2	61.096	61.140	0.10	1	1	3.3931
2	3	0	61.456	61.471	0.03	23	17	3.3753
1	3	1	66.059	66.051	0.02	272	187	3.1471
5	1	-1	66.499	66.453	0.11	19	27	3.1286
4	2	1	66.960	66.963	0.01	11	18	3.1054
2	1	-2	67.640	67.688	0.12	695	32	3.0731
5	2	0	68.200	68.138	0.15	13	11	3.0534
2	3	-1	68.661	68.676	0.04	35	0	3.0302
2	3	1	69.061	69.056	0.01	1000	1000	3.0140
6	1	0	70.362	70.392	0.07	101	37	2.9586
3	1	-2	72.203	72.202	0.00	47	56	2.8868
3	3	1	73.765	73.765	0.00	179	13	2.8277
5	2	-1	74.505	74.508	0.01	110	107	2.8005
2	2	2	76.367	76.327	0.11	20	26	2.7361
4	0	2	77.128	77.110	0.05	347	362	2.7094
4	1	-2	78.229	78.209	0.06	26	17	2.6728
7	1	0	81.752	81.765	0.04	30	33	2.5612
5	3	-1	86.517	86.499	0.06	51	15	2.4272

^{a)} $\Delta = |\sin^2 \Theta_{\text{theo.}} - \sin^2 \Theta_{\text{exp.}}| \cdot 1000$. ^{b)} I_{max} is normalized to 1000.

Table 23: $\text{Sm}_8\text{O}_9(\text{PO}_4)_2$. Indexing of the XRPD pattern (Cu- $\text{K}\alpha_1$) with the observed and theoretical diffraction angles of 14 reflections.

h	k	l	$4\Theta_{\text{exp.}} [^\circ]$	$4\Theta_{\text{theo.}} [^\circ]$	$\Delta^{\text{a)}}$	$I_{\text{exp.}}^{\text{b)}}$	$I_{\text{theo.}}^{\text{b)}}$	$d_{\text{theo.}} [\text{\AA}]$
1	1	0	18.733	18.740	0.00	95	449	9.4303
1	2	1	42.774	42.768	0.01	149	137	4.1516
3	2	1	50.881	50.906	0.05	120	146	3.4964
2	0	-2	55.293	55.248	0.09	794	832	3.2264
1	3	1	56.312	56.321	0.02	309	187	3.1661
6	0	0	57.649	57.611	0.08	628	617	3.0967
2	3	1	58.847	58.860	0.03	1000	1000	3.0324
3	3	-1	62.381	62.353	0.06	220	88	2.8664
6	0	-1	62.841	62.920	0.18	210	25	2.8412
4	0	2	65.616	65.629	0.03	433	364	2.7269
4	3	-1	67.453	67.416	0.09	443	438	2.6567
0	3	3	93.986	93.992	0.02	340	363	1.9318
8	3	1	97.020	97.009	0.04	240	212	1.8752
1	6	0	100.414	100.422	0.03	179	47	1.8154

^{a)} $\Delta = |\sin^2 \Theta_{\text{theo.}} - \sin^2 \Theta_{\text{exp.}}| \cdot 1000$. ^{b)} I_{max} is normalized to 1000.

Table 24: $\text{Gd}_8\text{O}_9(\text{PO}_4)_2$. Indexing of the powder diffraction pattern [4] with the values out of literature and theoretical diffraction angles of 11 reflections.

h	k	l	$4\Theta_{\text{lit.}} [^\circ]$	$4\Theta_{\text{theo.}} [^\circ]$	$\Delta^{\text{a)}}$	$I_{\text{lit.}}^{\text{b)}}$	$I_{\text{theo.}}^{\text{b)}}$	$d_{\text{theo.}} [\text{\AA}]$
1	1	0	18.833	18.883	0.04	140	454	9.3592
2	1	0	25.132	25.173	0.04	110	104	7.0269
1	2	1	43.107	43.119	0.02	160	136	4.1182
3	2	1	51.305	51.378	0.14	100	146	3.4648
1	3	1	56.744	56.769	0.05	300	187	3.1417
6	0	0	58.103	58.104	0.00	750	619	3.0710
2	3	1	59.363	59.353	0.02	1000	1000	3.0077
3	3	-1	62.822	62.778	0.10	180	87	2.8474
6	0	-1	63.322	63.332	0.02	200	25	2.8232
4	0	2	66.342	66.311	0.07	400	358	2.6996
4	3	-1	67.881	67.875	0.01	450	431	2.6392

^{a)} $\Delta = |\sin^2 \Theta_{\text{theo.}} - \sin^2 \Theta_{\text{exp.}}| \cdot 1000$. ^{b)} I_{max} is normalized to 1000.